

PETER SENN

The Lepidoptera of Gdynia

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Abstract: The Butterflies and Moths (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera, Heterocera) of the city of Gdynia (northern Poland). This survey of moths, the first ever carried out in Gdynia (northern Poland), covers the period from 2006 to 2018. It yielded a total of 1172 species: 1108 moths (94.5%) and 64 butterflies (5.5%). 236 species (20.1%) are first records for the province of Pomerania and a further 155 (13.3%) have not been recorded since the 19th or early 20th century. The records include 641 species of Microlepidoptera from 47 families, 467 species of Macrolepidoptera (macromoths) from 20 families, and 64 butterfly species from 5 families. The most numerous families are Geometridae (183 species), Noctuidae (167) and Tortricidae (160).

Key words: Lepidoptera, new data, Gdynia, faunistics.

INTRODUCTION

Since the publication of the review of the Lepidoptera of East and West Prussia by SPEISER (1903), and the later work by URBAHN & URBAHN (1939) dealing with the Lepidoptera of Pomerania within its pre-war (German) borders, hardly any scientific papers have been published on the occurrence and distribution of butterflies and moths, either in the present-day Polish province of Pomerania or in the so-called Tri-City – Gdańsk, Sopot and Gdynia. Earlier works in the Polish language that included this region (ROMANISZYN 1929 and KRZYWICKI 1982) merely replicated data from SPEISER. The first papers containing new data on this subject were published only after the turn of the century (KAŹMIERCZAK *et al.* 2006, SENN 2008, 2012, 2013 and SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012). The present survey covers moths photographed or trapped within the boundaries of the city of Gdynia between 2006 and 2018. For the sake of completion, the butterflies of Gdynia have been added, although these are dealt with in depth in the distribution atlas by SENN (2015).

STUDY AREA

Gdynia (centre – 54°31'N, 18°32'E) is a city on the Baltic Sea that came into being in the aftermath of World War I, when the revived Polish state decided to build its own port on the Gulf of Gdańsk, as the nearby port of Danzig (Gdańsk) was being operated by Germany.

It lies within two physiographic units – the Kashubian Coast and the Kashubian Lakeland (KONDRACKI 1981). The borderline between them follows the edge of the forest, where this meets the built-up area.

The eastern part of Gdynia, i.e. the districts within the Kashubian Coast area – Obłuże, Chylonia, Cisowa, City Centre, Orłowo and Mały Kack – lie at altitudes from zero to 50-60 m above sea level. This part of the city is highly urbanised with numerous industrial complexes. Within this physiographic unit there are the characteristic promontories and steep cliffs of Oksywie and Redłowo, with elevations of 30-50 m. On the latter there is a large forest (protected as a nature reserve). There are also parks on the Kamienna Góra Hill (City Centre) and at Kolibki (Orłowo).

The city's western districts, belonging to the Kashubian Lakeland, principally Witomino, Chwarzno-Wiczlino, Dąbrowa and Wielki Kack, lie at heights from ca 150 m to ca 200 m (Góra Donas) above sea level. The margins of the uplands belonging to the Kashubian Lakeland are bisected by erosional valleys (Marszewo, the River Kacza). Other watercourses include the Źródła Marii, Cisówka, Potok Kolibkowski and Swelinia streams, with three nature reserves in their valleys protecting riparian woodlands. The edge zones of the uplands are largely wooded – indeed, nearly half the city's area consists of forest, mostly of mixed beech, oak and pine. Urbanisation is encroaching upon these woodlands, causing them to become isolated (the land adjacent to them is being “developed”). Moreover, they are fragmented by the roads and railway lines running through them, although these can act as migration corridors. Edge communities (ecotones) are being eliminated, as housing developments are being built right up to the forest margin. Most of the woodlands lie within the boundaries of the Tri-City [Gdańsk, Sopot, Gdynia] Landscape Park.

There are still quite a number of meadows and a few small wetlands, but also many areas of so-called waste land. There is now little farming in Gdynia. Much arable land has been allowed to go fallow. Some of this has already been built upon, and more is scheduled for development, especially in the city's western areas.

Gdynia's climate is quite an equable one with an annual average temperature of 8-9°C. The coldest month is February (-1.3°C) and the warmest one is July (17.3°C). The growing season lasts for about 200 days. The city enjoys a large number of sunshine hours, especially in May and June. Humidity levels are fairly high. The wettest month is July (70 mm) and the driest one is March (23 mm). The prevailing winds blow from the west and south-west.

The municipal area of Gdynia lies within the UTM “squares” (Fig. 1): CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44 and CF45.

HABITATS

The following summarises the habitats in the 48 sites in the various districts of Gdynia where I photographed or collected butterflies and moths (see Figs. 1,2).

Chwarzno [CF34]

1. The walls beneath lamps on the Sokółka estate (Bu) (these and other abbreviations denoting habitats are explained on p. 10), and also the gardens on the estate and the grassy land between this and the nearby forest. Up to 2007 this land used to be fenced-in pasture where horses and cows would be put out to graze. Later, it gradually became built over, while the remaining open areas, now generally accessible, gradually turned into a dry meadow (Dm) with birch and pine saplings derived from the nearby forest trees encroaching onto it

Fig. 1. Map showing the position of UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator) squares in Gdynia (based on a map downloaded from <http://lepidoptera.eu/records2/Map.php> on 30.01.2017).

Ryc. 1. Mapa pokazująca układ kwadratów UTM (Universal Transverse Mercator) w Gdyni (na podstawie mapy pobranej z Wikipedii <http://lepidoptera.eu/records2/Map.php> z 30.01.2017).

little by little. Since 2016, however, the last remaining patches of this open ground have been built on. The lamps, formerly energy-saving bulbs which attracted moths, have been largely replaced by LED bulbs, the light of which does not attract insects. A lepidopterologically quite promising site has thus all but ceased to exist. Also in this locality is the balcony of my flat, where I set up my light screen and actinic light trap. I make a distinction between moths that were attracted to the lamps on the estate walls (Bu) and those that flew to the screen (Uv): some that I found at street level, like *Alucita hexadactyla*, never turned up on my balcony, and vice versa, e.g. *Apoda limacodes*. Included in this locality are the margins of the surrounding mixed woodland (Ma) with *Fagus sylvatica*, *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*, *Carpinus betulus* and *Betula pendula* among the broad-leaved species and *Pinus sylvestris* and *Picea abies* among the conifers. The great majority of macromoths and a fair proportion of the micromoths were found here, including some rare ones like *Roeslerstammia pronubella* (Roeslerstammidae). This locality is also where I found the first male of *Ditula angustiorana* (Tortricidae) in Poland (SENN & KOWALCZYK 2018).

Fig. 2. Positions of localities 1–48 monitored in Gdynia from 2006 to 2017 (based on a map downloaded from Google Maps <https://www.google.pl/maps/place/Gdynia> on 31.12.2016)

Ryc. 2. Położenie stanowisk od 1–48 kontrolowanych w Gdyni od 2006 do 2017 (na podstawie mapy pobranej z Google Maps <https://www.google.pl/maps/place/Gdynia> z 31.12.2016).

2. A very small wetland (Pt) by the Chwarzno-Sokółka bus terminus. Despite its small size and the tendency for litter to accumulate in it, it supports many typical riparian plant species, e.g. *Lythrum salicaria*, *Lycopus europaeus*, *Typha* sp. and *Salix* sp. and also lepidopteran species typical of such habitats, like *Phalonidia manniana* (Tortricidae), *Orthonama vittata* (Geometridae) and *Nonagria typhae* (Noctuidae).

3. Extensive former fields, now lying fallow and turning into waste ground (Wg) or dry meadows (Dm), between ul. [= street, road] Chwarznieńska and ul. Krauzego and the sandy ground formerly used by moto-cross enthusiasts. In late summer it is covered with *Solidago virgaureae*, so in spring there are moths like *Eucosma aspidiscana* (Tortricidae), whose caterpillars forage on goldenrod. There is also a woodland margin (Ma) around some waste ground with *Rubus* sp. and *Coptotriche marginea* (Tischeriidae).

Wiczlino [CF34]

4. A valley with meadows running parallel to ul. Wiclińska. Some years ago a narrow paved path was built along the valley in connection with the installation of drains in this part of the city. This led to the degradation of the meadows, which now resemble waste ground or scrub (Dm/Wg). This is the only part of the city where I have seen *Odezia atrata* (Geometridae) or *Hemaris tityus* (Sphingidae).

5. Waste ground (Wg) and the edges of damp meadows (Wm) by ul. Fregatowa. Here I found such interesting species as *Syncopacma larseniella* (Gelechiidae), *Enarmonia formosana* and *Epiblema graphana* (both Tortricidae) and *Acrobasis advenella* (Pyrilidae)

6. Overgrowing meadows and fields at Dębowa Góra (the black hiking trail from Chwarzno to Niemotowo).

7. A broad tract of open ground with *Carex* sp. through the forest beyond the Niemotowo bus terminus.

8. An extensive peatbog/birch swamp (Pt) with *Ledum palustre* (the only locality of this plant in Gdynia) as well as *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *V. uliginosus* and *V. vitis-idaea* in the forest between the Długa Rola fields and the road to Koleczkowo. There is also coniferous woodland with bilberries (Cw). This is where I found pupae of *Lyonetia ledi* (Lyonetiidae).

9. Two damp meadows (Wm) in the valley of the River Kacza bisected by the road leading to the Góra Donas hill. This is a good habitat for flowers like *Viola palustris*, *Caltha palustris*, *Polygonum bistorta*, *Filipendula ulmaria* and *Potentilla reptans*. Here I found butterflies like *Pyrgus malvae*, *Callophrys rubi*, *Brenthis ino* and *Boloria selene*, to name but a few, and also mines of the rare nepticulid *Stigmella filipendulae*.

10. An extensive damp meadow (Wm) (ca 15 ha) through which the River Kacza flows in its early course with abundant water-fringe vegetation (Wf) along its banks, e.g. *Lythrum salicaria*. The meadow is mown once a year, halting succession, so it is rich in the appropriate flora. It supports an equally rich lepidopteran fauna, e.g. *Papilio machaon* (Papilionidae), *Argynnis aglaja* and *A. adippe* (Nymphalidae), and also *Lythria cruentaria* (Geometridae).

11. A stretch of heathland (Ht) ca 1 ha in area (large patches of *Calluna vulgaris*) and a dry meadow (Dm) of about the same area adjoining it. This is the only such large piece of heathland in Gdynia, although it is becoming overgrown with *Cytisus scoparius*. The Lepidoptera here are typical of such habitats, e.g. *Scythris knochella* (Scythrididae), *Aristotelia ericinella* and *Neofaculta ericetella* (both Gelechiidae), *Plebejus idas* (Lycaenidae) and *Scotopteryx mucronata* (Geometridae). The meadow yielded the only mines I have of *Enteucha acetosa* (Nepticulidae) on *Rumex acetosa*. A house has now been built in one corner of the heath (it is privately owned), so the future of this habitat is uncertain.

Dąbrowa [CF33]

12. Fields and meadows (Wm) along the River Kacza on either side of ul. Wiczlińska. This is where I often found the first individuals of *Nymphalis xanthomelas* in the early spring.

13. A set-aside area of wetland (Pt) by ul. Miętowa. In recent years this has become less attractive with regard to typical wetland species, e.g. *Coenonympha tullia* and *Crambus uliginosellus*, as a long period without significant rainfall has caused it to dry out, with the loss of *Eriophorum* sp.

14. Sandy heathland (Ht) near the Góra Donas hill with *Calluna vulgaris*. Interesting, but poorer in species than the heath in Wiczlino. In danger of becoming overgrown with trees and shrubs. Species found here include *Aethes hartmanniana* (Tortricidae).

15. A large sandy area (Sg) on either side of the yellow hiking trail to the Góra Donas hill. Badly cut up by moto-cross enthusiasts, but the patches of vegetation that have survived intact include *Helichrysum arenarium* and *Lychnis viscaria*, and a number of interesting lepidopteran species, e.g. *Eublemma minutata* (Noctuidae) can still be found there.

16. An extensive damp meadow (Wm) several ha in area lying between coniferous woodland and riparian woodland with *Alnus glutinosa*, rich in both flora and lepidoptera. Mown once a year.

17. The other meadows in this district designated as set-aside areas.

18. A peatbog in the forest (Pt) by the yellow hiking trail leading to the Góra Donas hill and the surrounding woodland. This yielded such species as *Recurvaria leucatella* (Gelechiidae) and *Ancylis uncella* (Tortricidae).

Witomino [CF34]

19. The “Kacze Łęgi” nature reserve (riparian woodland, mainly *Alnus glutinosa* and *Ulmus* sp.) (Aw) by the Źródło Marii stream. Here I found mainly leaf-mining species, e.g. *Heliozela resplendella* (Heliozelidae), *Stigmella lemniscella* and *S. ulmivora* (Nepticulidae), also *Phyllonorycter schreberella* and *P. tristrigella* (Gracillariidae).

20. Meadows (Wm) by a woodland path from Witomino to Chwarzno. These yielded mines of *Stigmella aeneofasciella* on *Agrimonia eupatoria* and also a mine of *Bohemannia pulverosella* on a leaf of an apple tree.

21. Polana Krykulec – an overgrowing meadow (Dm) and scrub (Sc) beside a detention basin (dry pond) on the Źródło Marii stream.

22. Ul. Narcyzowa – the entrance porches to blocks of flats on this street (Bu). These buildings are close to the forest edge and moths are often attracted to the porch lights, from where they can be photographed or collected. One interesting species I found there and nowhere else was *Hecatera dysodea* (Noctuidae).

23. The 4 km long path through the mixed forest (species composition similar to that in locality 1) to Dęptowo (Mw). There I found numerous interesting species, especially in the open spaces among the trees. Examples include *Anania stachydalis* (Crambidae) and a pair of copulating *Agria tau* (Saturniidae).

Mały Kack [CF34]

24. The south-facing, strongly insolated slope of a railway embankment.

25. A damp meadow (ca 1 ha) by the River Kacza near ul. Sieradzka.

Wielki Kack [CF33]

26. The embankment between the railway line and the overgrowing Jezioro Kackie lake, destroyed by the recent reconstruction of the railway tracks (Rd). Before, this used to be one of the two or three localities in Gdynia, where butterflies associated with limestone areas could be found, e.g. *Cupido minimus* and *Polyommatus coridon*. The calcium in the soil by

the railway tracks would have been leached out of the ballast. As the work on the railway has been completed this site is now recovering.

27. The scrub (Sc) on the eastern side of the Tri-city by-pass.

28. The scrub, damp meadows and riparian woodland (Sc, Wm, Aw) on the western side of the Tri-city by-pass. This is one of the many sites of the protected *Lycaena dispar*; and where I also caught a number of micromoths associated with riparian woodland, e.g. *Nematopogon metaxella* (Adelidae), *Stathmopoda pedella* (Stathmopodidae), *Epinotia tenerana*, *Phiaris umbrosana* (Tortricidae) and *Epermenia illigerella* (Epermeniidae).

29. Meadows (Wm) and peatbogs (Pt) in the valley of the Żródło Marii stream.

30. Overgrowing waste ground (Wg) on former railway sidings. This site too boasts a few calciphilous species like *P. coridon*.

31. Meadows (Dm) near ul. Gnieźnińska (Gdańsk Osowa), close by the boundary with Gdynia. One of the few localities of *Limenitis camilla* (Nymphalidae) in the city. Also good for burnet moths (Zygaenidae).

32. A dry meadow surrounded by trees through which a railway siding once passed.

Orłowo [CF43]

33. The Kolibki Park (Pg) with a lot of interesting trees and shrubs including *Laburnum anagyroides*, *Tilia* sp., *Populus alba*, *Lonicera xylosteum* and *Symphoricarpos albus*. Here I found rare leaf miners like *Phyllocnistis xenia* (Gracillariidae).

34. The path below the cliff along the beach towards Sopot (Mw). Little sun reaches this place, so it is best for moths mining the leaves of Norway maple, beech, oak, lime, plum and laburnum.

35. Ul. Wrocławska – the park, once dilapidated, now “cleaned up”, around the new hotel and the elm scrub (Sc) in the neighbourhood. Also the riparian woodland (Aw) and damp meadows (Wm) beyond the end of this street.

36. The “Łęg nad Swelinia” nature reserve (Aw, Wm). Not much of lepidopteran interest here, apart from leaf miners.

Redłowo [CF44]

37. A large patch of waste ground (Wg) between primary school No. 13 and the expressway through Gdynia. This rapidly overgrowing land was once occupied by buildings. This is a good site for butterflies, e.g. *Cupido argiades* (Lycaenidae), on one side there is an embankment with *Prunus spinosa*.

38. The forest on the “Kępa Redłowska” [Redłowo Promontory] nature reserve (Mw). Also the walls of a block of flats (Bu) nearby.

39. Scrub (Sc) around the Polana Redłowska, a piece of open ground much frequented by grill enthusiasts.

City Centre [CF44]

40. Waste ground (Wg), a damp meadow (Wm) and woodland margins (Ma) around the “Arka” tennis courts. This has yielded some interesting butterflies – *Papilio machaon*, *Argynnis aglaja* and *Apatura ilia*, and moths – *Alloclementia mesospilella* (Incurvariidae) and *Pammene aurita* (Tortricidae).

41. The Maria and Lech Kaczyński Park on the Kamienna Góra hill (Pg). Interesting tree species here include *Ulmus* sp. and *Acer campestre* (the only locality I know of this species in the city), *Tilia* sp., *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *A. platanoides* and *Prunus cerasus*. Here I have come across the occasional butterfly, e.g. *Celastrina argiolus* (Lycaenidae), and some unusual leaf miners, especially on field maple – *Stigmella aceris* (Nepticulidae) and *Phyllonorycter acerifoliella* and *Caloptilia hemidactylella* (Gracillariidae).

42. Allotment gardens (Pg) and overgrowing, derelict railway sidings (Wg) parallel to ul. Jana z Kolna. Although close to the built-up area of the city, this place has yielded many interesting species, mostly butterflies (including *Lycaena dispar* (Lycaenidae)), but also *Stigmella freyella*, a rare miner of the leaves of *Calystegia sepium* that entwines the wire netting fences around the allotments, and *Phyllonorycter platani* on the leaves of one of the few mature plane trees in Gdynia.

Marszewo [CF34]

43. An extensive damp meadow (Wm) and the Forest Botanical Garden. The meadow used to be mown once a year, now it is grazed. It has yielded a good number of interesting species, like *Argynnis adippe* (Nymphalidae), *Grapholita jungiella* (Tortricidae) and *Xanthorhoe designata* (Geometridae).

Chylonia [CF34]

44. An alluvial woodland (Aw) and wet meadow (Wm) between the busy thoroughfare of ul. Morska and ul. Swarzewska. Despite the proximity of these streets and the fair number of walkers, this is still quite an interesting place for Lepidoptera.

Pogórze [CF34]

45. A dry meadow (Dm) with scattered trees and shrubs near ul. Platynowa. Apart from numerous butterflies, this is also the site where the clearwing moth *Pyropteron triannuliformis* (Sesiidae) was found.

Obluże [CF34]

46. Oak wood growing on the south-facing slope of the Oksywie Promontory.

47. A damp meadow (Wm) surrounded by coniferous woodland (Cw) near ul. Bosmańska.

Babie Doly [CF45]

48. Meadows (Dm) and scrub (Sc) between ul. Zielona and the cliff edge of the Oksywie Promontory. This is one of the few areas left within the city boundaries where crops are still grown.

Scrub (Sc). This term is used to describe former farmland that has been left fallow and that has become overgrown with young birch and pine trees, broom and other shrubs. There are larger or smaller areas of such habitat all over the city, and many of them have been built upon or are scheduled for “development”.

Woodlands. There are a number of different types of woodland in Gdynia. The predominant type is mixed (Mw), although the proportions of deciduous and coniferous trees can vary widely from one patch to another. The main broad-leaved trees in these mixed woodlands are beech *Fagus sylvatica*, sessile oak *Quercus petraea* and pedunculate oak *Q. robur*, particularly along their edges, and also hornbeam *Carpinus betulus* and birch *Betula pendula*. The principal coniferous trees are Scots pine *Pinus sylvestris* and spruce *Picea abies*. Other tree species present in smaller numbers include European larch *Larix decidua*, lime *Tilia* sp., elm *Ulmus* sp., Norway maple *Acer platanoides* and sycamore *Acer pseudoplatanus*. There are also coniferous woodlands (Cw) consisting of Scots pine and a ground layer predominantly of bilberries *Vaccinium myrtillus*, a well as very small areas of riparian woodland (Aw) along streams, consisting mainly of alder *Alnus glutinosa*. Finally, woodland margins (Ma) are very good places for finding butterflies and moths, not to mention other insects. Unfortunately, many new housing developments in the city are being built right up to the edge of adjacent woodland, thereby destroying these valuable ecotone communities. Apart from oaks, here we also find hazel *Corylus avellana*, rowan *Sorbus aucuparia*, dog rose *Rosa canina* and numerous species/varieties of plum and cherry *Prunus*, apple *Malus*

and pear *Pyrus communis*. Recently felled woodland (Fw) implies areas of woodland from which all or most of the original trees have been removed and which have become naturally colonised by tree saplings, broom bushes etc.

Lines or clumps of trees (Tr). Avenues of trees along roads (e.g. limes, sycamores) or clumps of trees (e.g. birches, conifers) in otherwise open terrain.

In addition to the parks already mentioned there are, obviously, gardens all over the city. There are several places with extensive areas given over to allotments, and half a dozen larger or smaller cemeteries (Pg).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This survey of the Lepidoptera of Gdynia took place from 2006 to 2018 at nearly 50 localities within the city boundaries, although a high proportion of the material was obtained in Chwarzno-Wiczlino, a district in the western part of the city. The criterion for recording a species as being present in the city was at least one record within its boundaries of any developmental stage (egg, caterpillar, pupa, mine or imago) during the thirteen years of the survey. From 2006 until 2014 the butterflies and moths were photographed, while in later years they were trapped at light using a 250 W mercury vapour bulb and white screen, in an actinic light trap placed on a balcony a short distance from a woodland margin, on bait (wine rope) or taken off the walls of buildings near estate lights after dark or in the early morning (most of the larger moths). Moths were also netted during the day on sight or after they had been flushed out of trees and shrubs (most of the micromoths). In addition, a good many species were identified on the basis of their caterpillars or mines.

All the records are in the form of photographs (only species definitively identifiable therefrom), voucher specimens (imagines) or herbarium specimens (mines). All the photographs are in the author's archive; some are available on the Biodiversity Map of Poland www.biomap.pl. The voucher and herbarium specimens are in the author's collection. Some voucher specimens have been donated to the Upper Silesian Museum, Bytom, Poland (USMB).

FREQUENCY

This survey covers a relatively small area. On this basis, therefore, it is therefore difficult if not downright risky to categorise species as "widespread, local, etc." and "abundant, infrequent etc.". This applies in particular to the imagines of non-leaf-mining micromoths, which were caught in one part of the city area, but not sought elsewhere. As far as the larger moths are concerned, there are those that turned up every year in accordance with their voltinism and flight times, sometimes in considerable numbers, whilst others appeared singly and just once or twice only during the survey period.

SPECIES NOT RECORDED

There are undoubtedly a number of species that are present in Gdynia but have not yet been recorded. This is probably due to the fact that not all habitats were explored to an equal extent. For example, there are several areas of thickly wooded, almost impenetrable peatbogs: some of the moths in these habitats would no doubt fly to an actinic trap or illuminated screen at night. The same applies to the four nature reserves within the city's borders. They are mostly quite thickly wooded areas, where not many moths let alone other insects fly during the daytime. Working on my own, it was not possible for me to deploy such traps or screens at night.

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Abbreviations:

Habitats: **Aw** – damp riparian woodland, **Bu** – buildings (interiors and outer walls), **Cw** – coniferous woodland, **Dm** – dry meadows, **Fw** – recently felled woodland, **Ht** – heathland, **Ma** – woodland margins, **Mw** – mixed woodland, **Pg** – parks, gardens, allotments and cemeteries, **Pt** – peatbogs and other wetlands, **Rd** – road and railway tracksides, **Sc** – scrub, **Sg** – sandy ground, **Tr** – lines or clumps of trees and/or shrubs, **Wf** – water-fringe vegetation, **Wg** – waste ground, **Wm** – wet (damp) meadows, **Uv** – UV/actinic light traps.

Developmental stage: **O** – egg, **L** – larva, **Lc** – larval case, **M** – mine, **P** – pupa, **Pex** – pupal exuvium, **Im** – imago, **ex l.** – ex larvae, **ex p.** – ex pupae.

PS – Peter Senn

SPECIES DESCRIPTIONS

Apart from the name of the species and its author, I give the code(s) of the UTM square(s) and habitat(s) (see the list of abbreviations) in which it was photographed and/or caught, the date (or earliest and latest dates) of its record(s) and the developmental form(s) (see the list of abbreviations). Unless otherwise stated, all specimens are “photo/leg. et det. PS”.

The species are listed in the same order as in the second edition of “A Distributional Checklist of the Lepidoptera of Poland” (BUSZKO & NOWACKI 2017). Localities are described by the UTM square number and habitat. First-ever records of species for the province of Pomerania (henceforth “Pomerania”) (in relation to the information given in the first edition of the Checklist (BUSZKO & NOWACKI 2000) are marked with a double asterisk (**) – there are 236 (20.1%) such species (178 (15.1%) since 2012). There are also 155 (13.2%) (70 (6.0%) since 2012)) first records apart from historical ones – these are shown by a single asterisk (*). Species that I recorded for the first time in Pomerania before 2012 bear the reference to the paper in which those records were published (SENN 2008, 2012, 2013, SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012). All the historical records (pre-1960) given for Pomerania are taken from SPEISER (1903) and URBAHN & URBAHN (1939). To help me with identification, I made use of a range of literature and websites. Where I was unable to identify a specimen, I turned to experts for assistance – they are mentioned in the Acknowledgements. In addition, one record is of a species bred from an imported pomegranate (‡). For the status elsewhere in Poland of all the species described here, the reader is referred to BUSZKO & NOWACKI (2017). The scientific names of plants follow RUTKOWSKI (2008).

RESULTS

This survey of moths, the first ever carried out in Gdynia (northern Poland), covers the period from 2006 to 2018. It yielded a total of 1172 species: 1108 moths (94.5%) and 64 butterflies (5.5%). 236 species (20.1%) are first records for the province of Pomerania and

a further 155 (13.3%) have not been recorded since the 19th or early 20th century. The records include 641 species of Microlepidoptera from 47 families, 467 species of Macrolepidoptera (macromoths) from 20 families, and 64 butterfly species from 5 families. The most numerous families are Geometridae (183 species), Noctuidae (167) and Tortricidae (160).

Table 1. Families of Lepidoptera in Gdynia
Tabela 1. Rodziny motyli stwierdzone w Gdyni

Family	total	**	After 2012	*	After 2012	Family	total	**	After 2012	*	After 2012
Micropterigidae	3	1	1	-	-	Momphidae	4	-	-	2	2
Eriocraniidae	6	2	2	1	1	Batrachedridae	1	-	-	-	-
Hepialidae	5	1	-	1	-	Coleophoridae	34	15	15	3	2
Nepticulidae	55	5	5	1	1	Cosmopterigidae	2	1	1	-	-
Opostegidae	1	1	1	-	-	Gelechiidae	49	27	23	9	6
Heliozelidae	2	-	-	-	-	Cossidae	1	-	-	1	-
Adelidae	11	4	3	3	2	Sesiidae	4	-	-	2	2
Incurvariidae	4	1	1	1	-	Limacodidae	2	-	-	-	-
Prodoxidae	2	1	1	1	-	Zygaenidae	6	-	-	1	1
Tischeriidae	3	-	-	-	-	Tortricidae	160	63	48	49	26
Psychidae	6	2	2	2	-	Choreutidae	2	1	-	1	-
Tineidae	16	7	5	7	3	Schreckensteiniidae	1	-	-	1	1
Roeslerstammidae	2	1	1	-	-	Epermeniidae	2	2	2	-	-
Bucculatricidae	9	2	2	-	-	Douglasiidae	1	-	-	1	1
Gracillariidae	65	9	4	1	-	Alucitidae	1	-	-	1	-
Ypsolophidae	5	3	2	1	1	Pterophoridae	16	3	2	3	2
Glyphipterigidae	3	3	2	-	-	Pyralidae	30	9	6	3	2
Acrolepiidae	3	2	1	-	-	Crambidae	61	11	9	1	-
Plutellidae	1	-	-	-	-	Hesperiidae	6	-	-	-	-
Yponomeutidae	11	8	7	2	1	Papilionidae	1	-	-	-	-
Argyresthidae	14	6	3	3	2	Pieridae	9	-	-	1	-
Lyonetiidae	2	-	-	-	-	Lycaenidae	19	-	-	-	-
Cemistomidae	4	1	-	-	-	Nymphalidae	29	-	-	-	-
Bedelliidae	1	-	-	-	-	Lasiocampidae	6	-	-	-	-
Ethmiidae	2	1	-	1	-	Endromidae	1	-	-	-	-
Elachistidae	9	8	8	1	-	Saturnidae	1	-	-	-	-
Depressariidae	19	14	7	2	-	Sphingidae	9	-	-	-	-
Chimabachidae	1	-	-	-	-	Drepanidae	11	-	-	-	-
Lypusidae	1	-	-	-	-	Geometridae	183	7	5	29	7
Oecophoridae	11	5	3	2	-	Notodontidae	19	1	-	5	-
Carcinidae	1	-	-	-	-	Erebidae	45	1	1	3	1
Autostichidae	1	1	-	-	-	Nolidae	8	-	-	4	2
Scythrididae	2	2	1	-	-	Noctuidae	167	3	3	5	4
Stathmopodidae	1	1	1	-	-	Total	1172	236	178	155	70

Micropterigidae HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855

- ***Micropterix aruncella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Wm; Im 30 V 2017. 1 ex. netted in a damp meadow with buttercups *Ranunculus* sp. Recorded in a few other provinces.
- M. aureatella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Ma, Mw; Im 18 V 2015 – 11 VI 2017; historical record from Gdańsk Oliwa.
- M. calthella* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33, CF34, CF43; Wm; Im 04 VI 2014 – 28 VI 2017.

Eriocraniidae TUTT, 1899

- ***Eriocrania chrysolepidella* ZELLER, 1851. CF34; Ma; M/L 22 V 2015 on *Carpinus betulus*. Recorded in three other provinces of Poland.
- E. cicacitrella* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1839). CF34; Ma; M 19 V 2015 on *Betula pendula*, det. JB.
- ***E. sangii* (WOOD, 1891). CF34; Ma; M/L 3 V 2014 – 13 V 2015 on *Betula pendula*. Recent data on this species from three other provinces.
- E. semipurpurella* (STEPHENS, 1835). CF34; Tr; M/L 9 – 21 V 2015 on *Betula pendula*.
- E. sparmannella* (BOSC, 1791). CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; M 9 VI 2014 – 16 VII 2015 on *Betula pendula*.
- **E. subpurpurella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma; M 25 V 2015 – 12 V 2018 on *Quercus petraea*. In the 19th century mines found at Dzierżążno near Kartuzy. At present, records from most provinces.

Hepialidae STEPHENS, 1829

- Triodia sylvina* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 10 VIII 2007 – 10 VIII 2018.
- Pharmacis fusconebulosa* (DEGEER, 1778). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VI 2013 – 28 VI 2015.
- ***P. lupulina* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Im 31 V 2008 – 3 VI 2015 (SENN 2012).
- Phymatopus hecta* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Aw, Ma; Im 9 VI 2008 – 27 VI 2017.
- **Hepialus humuli* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im (2 ♂♂) 13 VI 2007 – 21 VI 2008 (SENN 2008).

Nepticulidae STAINTON, 1854

- ***Enteucha acetosa* (STAINTON, 1851). CF34; Dm; M 2 IX 2015 on *Rumex acetosa*. Current records from nearly all other provinces.
- Stigmella aceris* (FREY, 1857). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg; M 4 X 2014 – 28 VIII 2017 on *Acer platanoides* and *A. campestre*.
- S. aeneofasciella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF34; Ma, Wm; M 6 IX – 11 X 2015 on *Agrimonia eupatoria*.
- S. anomalella* (GOEZE, 1783). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg, Rd, Wg, Sc; M 11 XI 2013 – 24 IX 2016 on *Rosa canina*.
- S. assimilella* (ZELLER, 1848). CF34; Ma; M 17 IX 2015 on *Populus tremula*.
- S. basiguttella* (HEINEMANN, 1862). CF34; Ma; M 28 IX 2015 on *Quercus petraea*.
- S. betulicola* (STAINTON, 1856). CF34; Ma, Mw, Pg, Tr; M 18 X 2014 – 1 X 2017 on *Betula pendula*.
- S. carpinella* (HEINEMANN, 1862). CF33, CF34; Mw; M 17 X 2015 – 20 IX 2017 on *Carpinus betulus*.
- S. confusella* (WOOD & WALSINGHAM, 1894). CF34; Pt; M 13 IX 2017 on *Betula pendula*.

- S. crataegella* (KLIMESCH, 1936). CF34; Sc; M 21 – 29 VII 2016 on *Crataegus* sp., det. JB.
- ***S. filipendulae* (WOCKE, 1871). CF34; Wm; M 20 IX 2015 on *Filipendula ulmaria*. Present-day records from a few other provinces.
- S. floslactella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Ma, Tr; M 2 VIII 2015 – 8 X 2017 on *Corylus avellana*.
- ***S. freyella* (HEYDEN, 1858). CF44; Pg; M 9 X 2015 on *Calystegia sepium*, growing over a metal net fence around an allotment garden. This species has been recorded in a few other provinces.
- S. glutinosae* (STANTON, 1858). CF33; Aw; M 4 X 2014 – 8 X 2017 on *Alnus glutinosa*; det. GB.
- S. hemargyrella* (KOLLAR, 1832). CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma, Mw; M 26 IX 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Fagus sylvatica*.
- S. hybnerella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg, Tr; M 1 X 2014 – 21 VII 2016 on *Crataegus* sp.
- S. lapponica* (WOCKE, 1862). CF34; Ma, Tr; M 17 – 19 IX 2017 on *Betula pendula*.
- S. lemnicella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Ma, Mw, Tr; M 22 X 2013 – 8 X 2017 on *Ulmus* sp.
- S. luteella* (STANTON, 1857). CF34; Ma, Mw, Pt, Tr; M 13 IX 2015 – 1 X 2017 on *Betula pendula* and *B. pubescens*.
- S. magdalenae* (KLIMESCH, 1950). CF34; Rd, Tr; M 10 VII 2016 – 13 VIII 2017 on *Sorbus aucuparia*.
- S. malella* (STANTON, 1854). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Pg, Tr; M 26 X 2014 – 8 X 2017 on *Malus* sp. and *Prunus cerasus*.
- S. microtheriella* (STANTON, 1854). CF33, CF34, CF44; Aw, Ma; M 12 X 2014 – 8 X 2017 on *Carpinus betulus* and *Corylus avellana*.
- S. minisculella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF34; Pg; M 9 IX 2015 on *Pyrus communis*.
- S. myrtillella* (STANTON, 1857). CF33, CF34; Cw; M 16 VII – 15 X 2015 on *Vaccinium myrtillus*.
- S. nylandriella* (TENGSTROM, 1848). CF34; Ma, Tr; M 2 VIII 2015 – 10 VII 2016 on *Sorbus aucuparia*.
- S. obliquella* (HEINEMANN, 1862). CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg, Tr; M 26 X 2014 – 9 X 2015 on *Salix alba*.
- S. oxyacanthella* (STANTON, 1854). CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Pg, Tr; M 29 IX 2014 – 8 X 2017 on *Crataegus* sp. and *Malus domestica*.
- S. plagicolella* (STANTON, 1854). CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Ma, Rd, Sc, Tr; M 22 X 2013 – 8 X 2017 on *Prunus* sp.
- S. pyri* (GLITZ, 1865). CF34; Pg, Rd, Tr; M 4 VIII 2015 – 22 VIII 2016 on *Pyrus communis*.
- S. roborella* (JOHANSSON, 1971). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Rd, Tr; M 8 X 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.
- S. ruficapitella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; M 19 VI 2014 – 16 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.
- S. salicis* (STANTON, 1854). CF34; Ma, Mw, Rd; M 2 VIII 2015 – 1 X 2017 on *Salix caprea* and *S. cinerea*.

- S. samiatella** (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Ma, Rd; M 10 X 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea*.
- S. speciosa** (FREY, 1857). CF34, CF44; Tr; M 15 X 2014 – 21 VI 2016 on *Acer pseudoplatanus* and *A. tataricum*.
- S. splendidissimella** (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Ma, Mw, Rd, Tr; M 15 X 2013 – 8 X 2017 on *Rubus* sp. and *Geum urbanum*.
- **S. sorbi** (STANTON, 1861). CF34; Ma, Rd; M 26 VI 2015 – 20 VI 2016 on *Sorbus aucuparia*. Current records from many other provinces.
- S. tiliae** (FREY, 1856). CF34, CF43; Ma, Pg, Rd; M 12 X 2014 – 7 X 2017 on *Tilia* sp.
- S. tityrella** (STANTON, 1854). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Mw; M 10 X 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Fagus sylvatica*.
- S. trimaculella** (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Rd; M 20 X 2014 on *Populus nigra*.
- S. ulmivora** (FOLOGNE, 1860). CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Mw, Pg, Rd; M 20 X 2014 – 8 X 2017 on *Ulmus* sp.
- Trifurcula immundella** (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Ht, Uv; M 14 X 2015 on *Cytisus scoparius*; Im 8 VII 2017.
- Bohemannia pulverosella** (STANTON, 1849). CF34; Ma; M 6 IX 2015 on *Malus* sp.
- Ectoedemia albifasciella** (HEINEMANN, 1871). CF34, CF44; Ma, Mw; M 9 X 2015 – 1 X 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.
- E. arcuatella** (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF34; Ma; M 11 IX 2015 on *Fragaria vesca*.
- E. argyropeza** (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw M 30 X 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Populus tremula*.
- E. atricollis** (STANTON, 1857). CF33, CF34, CF45; Ma, Rd, Tr; M 9 IX 2015 – 17 IX 2017 on *Malus* sp. and *Crataegus* sp.
- E. hannoverella** (GLITZ, 1872). CF43; Tr; M 9 XI 2014 on *Populus nigra*.
- **E. heringi** (TOLL, 1934). CF33, CF34; Ma, Rd; M 1 XI 2014 – 20 XI 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*. At present there are records from many other provinces.
- E. intimella** (ZELLER, 1848). CF34; Ma; M 15 XI 2015 – 29 X 2016 on *Salix caprea* and *S. cinerea*.
- E. occultella** (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw, Rd; M 9 IX 2015 – 1 X 2017 on *Betula pendula*; Im 20 V 2016; det. JB.
- E. septembrella** (STANTON, 1849). CF33, CF44; Sc, Wm; M 17 VII – 2 X 2015 on *Hypericum perforatum*.
- E. sericopeza** (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Ma, Rd; M 24 VI 2014 – 29 VI 2015 on *Acer platanoides*.
- E. subbimaculella** (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34, CF44, CF45; Ma M 1 XI 2014 – 16 X 2016 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.
- E. turbidella** (ZELLER, 1848). CF43; Pg; M 3 XI 2014 on *Populus x canescens*.
- *E. weaveri** (STANTON 1855). CF34; Cw; M 15 X 2015 on *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; SPEISER (1903) provided records of this species from Pomerania but without specifying localities. Nationwide, recorded in 13 of Poland's 16 provinces

Opostegidae MEYRICK, 1893

- **Opostega salaciella** (TREITSCHKE, 1833). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 13 VII 2015 – 18 VI 2016; det. JB. This species has been recorded in ten other provinces.

Heliozelidae HEINEMANN & WOCKE, 1877

Heliozela hammoniella SORHAGEN, 1885. CF33; Sc; M 17 X 2017 on *Betula pendula*.

H. resplendella (STAINTON, 1851). CF34; Aw; M 15 X 2016 on *Alnus glutinosa*.

Adelidae BRUAND, 1850

Nemophora degeerella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ma, Tr; Im 5 VI 2008 – 16 VI 2015.

N. metallica (PODA, 1761). CF34; Dm; Im 17 VII 2008 – 29 VII 2015.

**Adela croesella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF44; Aw, Ma; Im 3 VI 2014 – 18 VI 2017. Historical records from Gdańsk Stogi and Oliwa (SPEISER 1903). Elsewhere in Poland, records from nine provinces.

***A. cuprella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 20 – 22 V 2015. Current records from nine other provinces in Poland.

***A. reamurella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Ma; Im 3 V 2008 – 7 V 2015 (SENN 2012).

**Cauchas fibulella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Ma; Im 7 VI 2012 – 30 V 2015. SPEISER (1903) provides records from Gdańsk Orunia and Oliwa. Current records from almost all parts of Poland.

***C. rufifrontella* (TREITSCHKE, 1833). CF34; Dm; Im 29 V 2015; det. JB. Records to date from four other provinces of Poland.

***C. rufimitrella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF43; Wm; Im 12 V 2015 – 22 V 2017. Currently recorded from eight other provinces.

Nematopogon metaxella (HÜBNER, 1813). CF33; Aw; Im 27 VI 2017.

N. robertella (CLERCK, 1759). CF34, CF43; Bu, Sc, Ma; Im 1 V 2008 – 8 VI 2017.

**N. swammerdamella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43; Bu, Mw; Im 3 V 2008 – 8 V 2016 (SENN 2012).

Incurvariidae SPULER, 1898

***Alloclementia mesospilella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1854). CF44; Ma; Im V 2014; leg. JKK. Current records from four other provinces in eastern Poland.

**Incurvaria masculella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF44; Cw, Ma; Im 13 V 2008 – 20 V 2016; some specimens leg. JKK (SENN 2012).

I. pectinea HAWORTH, 1828. CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Pt, Tr; M 5 VII 2012 – 2 V 2014 on *Betula pendula*; Im 29 IV 2008 – 9 V 2016.

Phylloporia bistrigella (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Uv; Im 28 V 2016.

Prodoxidae RILEY, 1881

**Lampronia capitella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Pg, Tr; Im 6 VI 2008 – 5 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

***L. flavimitrella* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Bu; Im 20 V 2016; det. JB. Contemporary records from seven other provinces.

Tischeriidae SPULER, 1898

Tischeria dodonea STAINTON, 1858. CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; M 8 X 2014 – 28 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.

T. ekebladella (BJERKANDER, 1795). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Pg; M 10 X 2014 – 29 X 2016 on *Quercus petraea*, *Q. robur* and *Castanea sativa*; Im 12 VI 2008 – 20 VI 2016.

Coptotriche marginea (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Rd, Sc; M 25 VI 2014 – 2 X 2016 on *Rubus* sp.; Im 14 VI 2016.

Psychidae BOISDUVAL, 1828

Narycia duplicella (GOEZE, 1783). CF34; Bu; Im 9 VI 2016; det. JB.

***Dahlica triquetrella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Pex 27 IV 2011; det. KM. This species has been recorded in most other provinces.

***Siederia listerella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Wg; Im 6 – 8 V 2016; det. JB. Current records from eight other provinces.

Taleporia tubulosa (RETZIUS, 1783). CF34; Bu, Tr; Lc 22 IV 2013 – 12 V 2014; Im 25 V 2014 – 5 VI 2016.

**Psyche casta* (PALLAS, 1767). CF33, CF34, CF43; Bu, Tr, Wg; Lc 13 VI 2008 – 13 III 2011; Im I VII 2015; det. JB (SENN 2012).

**Bijugis bombycella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VI 2008 – 19 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

Tineidae LATREILLE, 1810

***Morophaga choragella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 27 VI 2008 – 24 VII 2017 (SENN 2012).

***Triaxomera fulvimitrella* (SODOFSKY, 1830). CF34; Rd, Bu; Im 8 VI 2008 – 8 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

**T. parasitella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 6 VI 2008 – 5 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

**Nemapogon clematella* (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VII 2014. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Current records from almost every other province in Poland.

**N. cloacella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 6 VI 2010 – 14 VI 2016; det. JB (SENN 2012).

**N. granella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 28 V 2008 (SENN 2012).

***N. variatella* (CLEMENS, 1859). CF34; Bu; Im 5 VII 2016; det. JB. Present in most other provinces, but not those along the northern border of Poland.

**Tineola bisseliella* (HUMMEL, 1823). CF34; Uv; Im 16 IX 2015; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Current records from almost the entire country.

***Tinea columbariella* WOCKE, 1877. CF34; Uv; Im 4 VII 2015; det. JB. Also CF43 (Gdańsk Oliwa); Bu; Im 7 V 2015, det. JB. Species recorded in eight other provinces.

**T. pellionella* LINNAEUS, 1758. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 4 – 7 VII 2015; det. JB. Also CF42 (Gdańsk Wrzeszcz); Bu; Im 22 VI 2016. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in nearly all other provinces.

**T. semifulvella* HAWORTH, 1828. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 17 VII 2008 – 7 VII 2017 (SENN 2012).

T. trinotella THUNBERG, 1794. CF34; Bu; Im 1 VI 2011.

***Nitidinea fuscella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VIII 2012; det. XD. Recorded in nearly all other provinces.

***Monopis imella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Uv; Im 2 VIII 2017; det. JB. Recorded in most other provinces.

***M. laevigella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 3 X 2012 – 25 VIII 2017; det. JB. Recorded in nearly all other provinces.

M. monachella (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VIII 2011 – 9 VIII 2013.

Roeslerstammidae BRUAND, 1850

Roeslerstammia erxlebelli (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Tr; Im 18 V 2017.

***R. pronubella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Ma; Im 17 V 2017. Recorded in a few provinces in central, eastern and southern Poland.

Bucculatricidae WALLENGREN, 1881

Bucculatrix bechsteinella (BECHSTEIN & SCHARFENBERG, 1805). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Ht, Rd, Sc, Tr; M 1 X 2014 – 16 IX 2017 on *Crataegus* sp., *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Malus* sp. and *Pyrus communis*; Im 25 V – 25 VI 2016; det. JB.

B. cidarella (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF43; Rd; M 24 IX 2016 – 24 VIII 2017 on *Alnus glutinosa*; Im 28 VI 2017.

B. demaryella (DUPONCHEL, 1840). CF34; Ma, Pt; M 9 XI 2015 – 13 IX 2017 on *Betula pendula*.

B. frangutella (GOEZE, 1783). CF33, CF34; Ma, Pt; M 9 IX 2015 – 20 IX 2017 on *Frangula alnus*.

***B. gnaphaliella* (TREITSCHKE, 1833). CF34; Ht; Im 5 VI 2015; det. JB. This species has been recorded all over Poland, except in the southern provinces.

***B. nigricomella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Rd; M 10 – 17 VII 2016 on *Leucanthemum vulgare*; det. JB. Recorded in most other provinces of Poland.

B. noltei PETRY, 1912. CF34; Dm, Ma; M 2 – 13 IX 2015 on *Artemisia vulgaris*.

B. thoracella (THUNBERG, 1794). CF34, CF43; Mw, Pg, Rd, Tr; M 1 XI 2014 – 7 X 2017 on *Fagus sylvatica* and *Tilia* sp.; Im 9 VI 2016.

B. ulmella ZELLER, 1848. CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw; M 7 X 2014 – 1 X 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.

Gracillariidae STANTON, 1854

Caloptilia elongella (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33; Aw; M 22 VII – 9 IX 2015 on *Alnus glutinosa*.

***C. fidella* (REUTTI, 1853). CF34; Pg; M 9 IX 2016 on *Humulus lupulus*. This species has been recorded in most other provinces.

C. hemidactylella (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF44; Pg; M 28 VIII 2017 on *Acer campestre*.

***C. populetorum* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Rd; M 22 VIII 2016 on *Betula pendula*. Recorded in all the other provinces.

C. rufipennella (HÜBNER, 1796). CF44; Ma; Im V 2015; leg. JKK, det. JB.

C. stigmatella (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF33, CF34, CF43; Aw, Bu, Ma, Rd, Wg; M 10 X 2014 – 24 VIII 2017 on *Populus tremula*, *Salix alba*, *S. caprea* and *S. viminalis*; Im 3 VIII 2014.

Gracillaria syringella (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF33, CF34, CF45; Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Tr; M 22 VI 2015 – 2 X 2016 on *Syringa vulgaris*, *Ligustrum vulgare* and *Fraxinus excelsior*; Im 4 VI 2015 – 18 V 2017.

**Aspilapterix tringipennella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 17 V 2008 – 28 VII 2014 (SENN 2012).

- Euspilapteryx auroguttella* STEPHENS, 1835. CF33; Wm; M 7 X 2015 on *Hypericum perforatum*.
- ***Calybites phasianipenella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu, Wm; Im 3 VIII 2008 – 2 VII 2017 (SENN 2012).
- ***Acrocercops brongniardella* (FABRICIUS, 1798). CF33; Aw; M 25 VI 2015 – 18 VI 2017 on *Quercus petraea* (SENN 2012).
- Leucospilapteryx omisella* (STAINTON, 1848). CF34; Ma, Wg; M 13 IX 2015 – 22 VIII 2016 on *Artemisia vulgaris*.
- Callisto denticulella* (THUNBERG, 1794). CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma, Pg, Rd, Tr; M 24 X 2014 – 21 VIII 2015 on *Malus* sp.; Im 25 VI 2015.
- Parornix anglicella* (STAINTON, 1850). CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Tr; M 29 IX 2014 – 10 VII 2016 on *Crataegus* sp.; Im 19 V 2015 – 18 V 2016; det. JB.
- P. betulae* (STAINTON, 1854). CF34; Ma, Tr; M 18 X 2014 – 27 IX 2015 on *Betula pendula*.
- P. carpinella* (FREY, 1863). CF34; Tr; M 6 IX 2015 on *Carpinus betulus*.
- P. devoniella* (STAINTON, 1850). CF34; Ma, Uv; M 12 X 2014 on *Corylus avellana*; Im 24 – 28 V 2016; det. JB.
- P. fagivora* (FREY, 1861). CF34; Ma; M 10 X 2014 on *Fagus sylvatica*; Im 5 VI 2017; det. JB.
- P. finitimella* (ZELLER, 1850). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Rd, Sc, Tr; M 16 X 2013 – 26 X 2016 on *Prunus domestica* and *P. spinosa*; Im 27 VI 2016 – 6 VII 2017; det. JB.
- P. scoticella* (STAINTON, 1850). CF34; Ma, Rd, Tr; M 18 VII – 6 X 2015 on *Malus* sp., *Sorbus aucuparia* and *S. aria*.
- Phyllonorycter apparella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF34; Ma, Rd; M 8 VII – 9 VIII 2015 on *Populus tremula*.
- P. blancardella* (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Ma; M 24 VI 2015 – 23 X 2016 on *Malus* sp.
- P. cavella* (ZELLER, 1846). CF33, CF34; Ma, Pt; M 19 X 2013 – 16 IX 2017 on *Betula pendula* and *B. pubescens*.
- P. cerasicolella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF33, CF34, CF45; Ma, Pg, Rd; M 7 X 2015 – 26 IX 2017 on *Prunus cerasus*.
- P. comparella* (DUPONCHEL, 1843). CF43; Pg; M 12 VII 2015 – 8 X 2017 on *Populus alba*; Im ex p. 30 VII 2017.
- P. connexella* (ZELLER, 1846). CF34, CF44; Rd, Sc; M 22 X 2013 – 15 X 2016 on *Populus nigra* and *Salix* sp.
- P. coryli* (NICELLI, 1851). CF34, CF43; Ma, Pg; M 14 X 2013 – 20 VII 2017 on *Corylus avellana*; Im ex p. 8 VIII 2017.
- P. corylifoliella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; M 7 VII 2015 – 31 VIII 2016 on *Betula pendula*.
- P. dubitella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF34; Rd; M 26 IX 2017 on *Salix caprea*; Im 10 V 2016 – 2 IV 2018 (ex l.); det. JB.
- P. esperella* (GOEZE, 1783). CF34, CF44; Tr; M 12 X 2014 – 16 IX 2017 on *Carpinus betulus*.
- P. emberizaepenella* (BOUCHÉ, 1834). CF34, CF43; Ma, Tr; M 8 VII 2015 – 6 VII 2017 on *Lonicera xylosteum* and *Symphoricarpos alba*; Im 20 VI 2016 – 14 VII 2017 (ex p.); det. JB.
- P. froelichiella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Aw, Ma, Wf; M 6 – 27 IX 2015 on *Alnus glutinosa*; Im 11 VI 2016 – 18 VI 2017.

- P. geniculella*** (RAGONOT, 1874). CF34, CF43; Ma, Pg, Tr; M 14 X 2013 – 7 X 2017 on *Acer pseudoplatanus*.
- P. harrisella*** (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; M 12 X 2014 – 4 X 2015 on *Quercus petraea*; Im 19 V 2015 – 5 VI 2017.
- P. heegeriella*** (ZELLER, 1846). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw; M 5 X 2014 – 22 VII 2015 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*; Im 28 VII 2016.
- P. insignitella*** (ZELLER, 1846). CF34; Dm; M 28 IX 2015 on *Trifolium pratense*.
- P. issikii*** (KUMATA 1963). CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Mw, Pg, Tr; M 12 X 2014 – 7 X 2017 on *Tilia* sp.
- P. joannisi*** (LE MARCHAND, 1936). CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Mw, Pg, Rd, Tr; M 13 X 2013 – 19 IX 2017 on *Acer platanoides*; Im 23 VII 2017.
- P. junoniella*** (ZELLER, 1846). CF34; Pt; M 2 V 2016 on *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*.
- P. klemannella*** (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF33, CF34; Aw, Ma; M 26 X 2014 – 9 IX 2015 on *Alnus glutinosa*; Im 11 V 2016.
- P. lautella*** (ZELLER, 1846). CF33, CF34; Ma; M 4 – 15 X 2015 on *Quercus petraea*.
- ***P. leucographella*** (ZELLER, 1850). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Rd, Tr; M 7 X 2014 – 3 IX 2017 on *Sorbus aucuparia*, *S. intermedia*, *S. aria*, *Fagus sylvatica*, *Prunus cerasus*, *Pyracantha coccinea* and *Malus* sp.; Im 7 VI 2008 (SENN 2008).
- P. maestingella*** (MÜLLER, 1764). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Mw; M 10 X 2014 – 20 IX 2017 on *Fagus sylvatica*; Im 2 V 2016 – 14 V 2017.
- P. nicellii*** (STAINTON, 1851). CF34; Ma; M 12 X 2014 on *Corylus avellana*.
- P. oxyacanthae*** (FREY, 1856). CF34, CF44; Ma, Sc; M 20 X 2014 – 2 X 2015 on *Crataegus* sp. and *Pyrus communis*.
- ***P. platani*** (STAUDINGER, 1850). CF44; Tr; M 16 XI 2009 – 16 XI 2017 on *Platanus acerifolia* (SENN 2012).
- P. populifoliella*** (TREITSCHKE, 1833). CF44; Tr; M 7 VII 2015 on *Populus nigra*.
- P. quercifoliella*** (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw, Tr; M 8 X 2014 – 1 X 2017 on *Quercus petraea* and *Q. robur*.
- P. rajella*** (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF43; Sc, Tr, Wm; M 27 IX 2015 – 9 IX 2016 on *Alnus glutinosa*; Im 27 V – 3 VI 2017.
- P. roboris*** (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF44; Ma, Mw; M 16 X 2016 – 16 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea*.
- P. sagitella*** (BIERKANDER, 1790). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma; M 5 X 2014 – 16 IX 2017 on *Populus tremula*.
- P. salicicolella*** (SIRCOM, 1848). CF33, CF34; Aw, Ma, Rd; M 25 X 2014 – 4 X 2015 on *Salix caprea* and *S. cinerea*.
- P. salictella*** (ZELLER, 1839). CF34, CF44; Ma, Tr; M 20 X 2014 – 9 X 2015 on *Salix alba* and *S. viminalis*.
- P. schreberella*** (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Mw, Tr; M 20 X 2014 – 28 IX 2015 on *Ulmus* sp.
- P. sorbi*** (FREY, 1855). CF33, CF34; Ma, Pg, Rd; M 26 VI 2015 – 10 VII 2016 on *Prunus* sp., *Sorbus aria* and *S. aucuparia*.
- P. stettinensis*** (NICELLI, 1852). CF33, CF34, CF43; Tr, Wf; M 17 VII 2015 – 24 VIII 2017 on *Alnus glutinosa*.

- P. tenerella* (JOANNIS, 1915). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Tr; M 28 IX 2008 – 20 IX 2017 on *Carpinus betulus*; Im 4 V 2014 – 29 V 2016.
- P. tristrigella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Pg, Tr; M 17 VII 2015 – 8 X 2017 on *Ulmus* sp.
- P. ulmifoliella* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF33, CF34; Ma, Pt, Tr; M 8 X 2014 – 19 IX 2016 on *Betula pendula*.
- ***Macrosaccus robiniella* (CLEMENS, 1859). CF34, CF43, CF44; Pg, Rd; M 23 X 2014 – 16 X 2017 on *Robinia pseudoacacia* (SENN 2012).
- Cameraria ohridella* DESHKA & DIMIĆ, 1986. CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Pg; M 22 IX 2015 – 20 IX 2017 on *Aesculus hippocastanum*; Im 8 V 2015 – 19 VII 2016.
- ***Phyllocnistis labyrinthella* (BJERKANDER, 1790). CF33, CF34; Ma, Rd; M 19 VIII – 15 IX 2015 on *Populus tremula*. Recorded in six other provinces.
- P. saligna* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34, CF43; Ma, Pg, Rd; M 20 X 2014 – 20 IX 2015 on *Salix alba*.
- P. unipunctella* (STEPHENS, 1834). CF34, CF44. CF45; Ma, Rd, Tr; M 7 VII 2015 – 17 IX 2017 on *Populus nigra*.
- ***P. xenia* M. HERING, 1936. CF43; Pg; M 25 VIII 2016 – 7 X 2017 on *Populus alba*. Known from a few other provinces.

Ypsolophidae GUENÉE, 1845

- Ypsolopha asperella* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 20 III 2015; det. AL.
- ***Y. dentella* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2010 – 3 VIII 2015 (SENN 2012).
- ***Y. parenthesesella* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VIII 2015. Recorded in all other provinces of Poland.
- **Y. sequella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 17 VI 2013 – 30 VII 2014. Historical records from Gdańsk and Świbno (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in eight other provinces.
- ***Ochsenheimeria urella* FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1842. CF33; Sc; Im 1 IX 2015; leg. JKK. det. JB. Recent records from only two other provinces.

Glyphipterigidae STANTON, 1854

- ***Glyphipterix bergstraesserella* (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Sc; Im 10 VI 2009 – 15 V 2016 (SENN 2012).
- ***G. forsterella* (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF33, CF34; Ma, Fw with *Carex* sp.; Im 14 VI 2015 – 11 VI 2017. Current records from most other provinces.
- ***G. simplicella* (STEPHENS, 1834). CF34; Dm, Ma, Wm; Im 21 V 2015 – 30 V 2017. Recent records from the majority of other provinces

Acrolepiidae HEINEMANN, 1870

- ***Digitivalva reticulella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 4 VI 2008 – 30 VII 2014 (SENN 2012).
- Acrolepia autumnitella* CURTIS, 1838. CF33; Wf; M 22 IX 2016 on *Solanum dulcamara*.
- ***Acrolepiopsis assectella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 5 VII 2012; det. AL. Present in almost all provinces of Poland.

Plutellidae GUENÉE, 1845

Plutella xylostella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Dm, Ht, Bu, Wf, Wm; Im 20 VIII 2009 – 7 IX 2016.

Yponomeutidae STEPHENS, 1829

Yponomeuta cagnagella (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Rd; L 2 VI 2016 and P 26 VII 2017, both on *Euonymus europaeus*; Im 27 VII 2015 – 16 VII 2017.

**Y. evonymella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2008 – 13 VII 2015 (SENN 2012).

***Y. malinellus* (ZELLER, 1838). CF34; Rd; L 18 VI 2016 on *Malus* sp. Records from the whole of Poland.

***Y. padella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Rd, Sc, Uv; L 6 VI 2016 on *Crataegus* sp.; Im 4 VIII 2015 – 28 VII 2017. Current records from nearly all provinces.

***Y. plumbella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Tr; Im 22 VII 2010 – 28 VII 2013 (SENN 2012).

***Swammerdamia caesiella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Pt; M/L 19 IX 2016 on *Betula pendula*. Records from the whole of Poland.

***S. pyrella* (VILLERS, 1789). CF34; Uv; Im 24 V 2016 – 18 V 2017. Records from practically the whole of Poland.

***Paraswammerdamia nebulella* (GOEZE, 1783). CF34; Sc; Im 16 VII 2017; det. JB. Recorded in many other provinces.

**Cedestis gyssemiella* ZELLER, 1839. CF33; Sc; Im 4 VIII 2016; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia. Present-day records from nearly all other provinces.

***Ocnerosstoma friesei* SVENSSON, 1966. CF34; Bu, Ma, Sc; Im 6 V 2016 – 2 VI 2017; det. JB. Recorded in nearly the whole country.

***O. piniariella* ZELLER, 1847. CF34; Sc; Im 14 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from most provinces.

Argyresthidae BRUAND, 1850

**Argyresthia albistria* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VII 2012 – 13 VIII 2015. Historical record from Pruszcz Gdański (SPEISER 1903). Currently recorded in most provinces.

***A. bergiella* (RATZEBURG, 1840). CF34; Pt; Im 8 VII 2016; det. JB. Current records from just three other provinces.

A. bonnetella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Tr; Im 17 VIII 2017; det. JB. Current records from most other provinces.

A. brockeella (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 10 VII 2010 – 19 VII 2014.

**A. curvella* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Rd; Im 12 VII 2010 – 27 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

***A. dilectella* ZELLER, 1847. CF34; Bu; Im 15 VII 2010 – 27 VII 2012 (SENN 2012).

A. glabratella (ZELLER, 1847). CF34; Ma, Rd, Sc; Im 2 VI 2016 – 25 VI 2017; det. JB.

A. goedartella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ma, Tr, Uv; Im 24 VI 2008 – 10 VII 2016.

***A. pruniella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Rd, Sc, Tr; Im 7 VIII 2008 – 17 VIII 2017 (SENN 2012).

***A. pygmaeella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Sc; Im 18 VI 2014; det. AL. Recorded in a few other provinces in various parts of Poland.

- ***A. retinella* ZELLER, 1839. CF33, CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 8 VII 2014 – 18 VII 2017; det. JB. Recorded in various parts of Poland.
- A. semitestacella* (CURTIS, 1833). CF33, CF34; Ma, Wg; Im 30 VIII 2015 – 10 VIII 2016.
- **A. spinosella* STAINTON, 1849. CF34; Ma, Pg, Rd, Uv; Im 13 VI 2008 – 7 VII 2017 (SENN 2012).
- ***A. trifasciata* STAUDINGER, 1871. CF34; Bu, Pg, Sc, Uv; Im 20 VI 2010 – 24 V 2016 (SENN 2012).

Lyonetiidae STAINTON, 1854

- Lyonetia clerkella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Tr, Uv; M 22 X 2013 – 15 XI 2015 on *Betula pendula*, *Crataegus* sp., *Malus* sp., *Prunus avium*, *P. domestica*, *Pyracantha coccinea*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *S. intermedia*; Im 26 VII 2016. Also CF12; Pg; M 11 IX 2016 on *Cydonia* sp.
- L. ledi* WOCKE, 1859. CF34; Pt; P 2 V 2016 on *Ledum palustre*.

Cemiostomidae

- Leucoptera laburnella* (STAINTON, 1851). CF33, CF43; Ma, Pg, Uv; M 3 XI 2014 – 22 IX 2015 on *Laburnum anagyroides*; Im 6 VII 2015 – 18 VII 2017; det. JB.
- L. lustratella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1855). CF33; Wm; M 17 VII 2015 on *Hypericum perforatum*.
- ***L. malifoliella* (O. COSTA, 1836). CF34, CF44; Ma, Sc, Tr; M 2 VIII 2015 – 6 VII 2017 on *Malus* sp., *Sorbus aucuparia*; Im 23 VII 2017. Recorded in most provinces.
- L. spartifoliella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Ht, Ma, Rd, Sc; M 20 IX – 14 X 2015 on *Cytisus scoparius*; Im 18 VI – 1 VII 2016.

Bedelliidae MEYRICK, 1880

- Bedellia somnulentella* (ZELLER, 1847). CF33; Wm; M 1 IX 2015 on *Calystegia sepium*.

Ethmiidae BUSCK, 1909

- **Ethmia bipunctella* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2009 – 16 VIII 2011 (SENN 2012).
- ***E. terminella* T. FLETCHER 1938. CF34; Bu, Rd, Uv; Im 2 VI 2008 – 18 VI 2016 (SENN 2012).

Elachistidae BRUAND, 1851

- ***Elachista albidella* NYLANDER, 1848. CF33, CF34; Aw, Pt; Im 27 VI – 16 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from seven other provinces.
- ***E. albifrontella* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF33, CF34; Aw, Dm, Sc, Tr; Im 23 VI 2016 – 19 VI 2017; det. JB. Recorded in most other provinces.
- **E. argentella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF33, CF34; Sc; Im 30 V 2008 – 25 V 2016 (SENN 2012).
- ***E. bifasciella* TREITSCHKE, 1833. CF34; Mw; Im 11 VI 2017. Recorded in five other provinces.
- ***E. humilis* ZELLER, 1850. CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma, Tr, Wg; Im 13 V 2016 – 9 VII 2017; det. JB. Contemporary records from eight other provinces.
- ***E. maculicerusella* (BRUAND, 1859). CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma, Bu, Sc, Uv, Wg, Wm; Im 9 VIII 2013 – 24 VII 2017. A common species, recorded in nearly all of Poland.

- ***E. pollinariella* ZELLER, 1839. CF33, CF34; Ma, Dm, Rd, Sc; Im 2 VI 2015 – 5 VI 2017. Recorded in most other provinces.
- ***E. subalbidella* SCHLÄGER, 1847. CF33; Aw; Im 27 VI 2017. Current records from seven other provinces.
- ***E. utonella* FREY, 1856. CF34; Sc; Im 10 VII 2016; det. JB. Recorded in a few other provinces.

Depressariidae MEYRICK, 1883

- ***Semioscopis steinkellneriana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Im 30 IV 2007 – 15 V 2015 (SENN 2008).
- ***Luquetia lobella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VI 2008 – 19 VII 2015 (SENN 2012).
- **Exaeretia allisella* STANTON, 1849. CF34; Bu; Im 28 VII 2008 – 3 VIII 2017 (SENN 2012).
- ***Agonopterix arenella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 7 V 2008 – 21 III 2017 (SENN 2012).
- A. assimilella* (TREITSCHKE, 1832). CF34; Ma; L 15 V 2016 on *Cytisus scoparius*.
- **A. heracliana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 17 III 2015 – 31 III 2017; det JB (SENN 2012).
- ***A. hypericella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu, Ma, Sc; Im 10 IV 2015 – 15 VIII 2017; det. JB. Recent records from seven other provinces.
- A. laterella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 29 III 2009 – 14 II 2017.
- ***A. multiplicella* (ERSCHOFF, 1877). CF34; Bu; Im 26 IV 2008 – 10 IX 2016 (SENN 2012).
- ***A. ocellana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 1 IV 2008 – 9 IV 2017 (SENN 2008).
- ***A. propinquella* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu; Im 29 VIII 2015; det. JB. Recorded in practically all provinces.
- A. purpurea* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Pg, Rd; Im 6 V 2015 – 10 V 2016.
- ***A. subpropinquella* (STANTON, 1849). CF34; Bu; Im 10 III 2015 – 3 IV 2016; det JB. Recorded in just three other provinces in south-west Poland.
- ***Depressaria badiella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IX 2015; det. JB. Recorded in a few other provinces south of Pomerania.
- ***D. chaerophylli* ZELLER, 1839. CF34; Bu; Im 10 VI 2014; det. AL. Recorded in various other parts of Poland.
- ***D. depressana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu, Rd, Sc, Uv; Im 3 VI – 22 VIII 2016. Records from many other regions of Poland.
- ***D. emeritella* STANTON, 1849. CF34; Bu; Im 24 IV 2008 – 19 IX 2015; det. TB (SENN 2012).
- ***D. olerella* ZELLER, 1854. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 29 IV 2010 – 6 VI 2015; det. JB (SENN 2012).
- ***D. radiella* (GOEZE, 1783). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 5 V 2008 – 26 V 2015. Recorded in most other provinces.

Chimabachidae HEINEMANN, 1870

- Diurnea fagella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 20 IV 2008 – 15 V 2017; both ♂♂ and ♀♀; also the dark form *dormoyella*.

Lypusidae HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1857

Agnoea josephinae (TOLL, 1956). CF34, CF44; Bu, Mw; Im 12 VI 2015 – 6 VI 2017.

Oecophoridae BRUAND, 1851

Schiffermuelleria schaefferella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 29 V 2013.

***Denisia similella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Ma, Bu; Im 19 VI 2014 – 25 VI 2017. Recorded in the whole of Poland.

D. stipella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ma; Im 27 VI 2015; det. JB.

**Metalampra cinnamomea* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VIII 2008 – 28 VI 2015 (SENN 2012).

**Endrosis sarcitrella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VI 2008 – 13 VI 2015 (SENN 2012).

***Hofmannophila pseudospretella* (STANTON, 1849). CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 18 V 2008 – 12 VI 2018 (SENN 2012).

***Borkhausenia fuscescens* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 13 VII 2015 – 31 VII 2016; det. JB. Recorded in five other provinces.

B. minutella (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Pt; Im 25 VI 2013 – 3 VI 2017.

***Crassa tinctella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF33, CF34; Ma, Pt, Uv; Im 15 VI 2009 – 21 VI 2017 (SENN 2012).

***Oecophora bractella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Ma, Tr; Im V 2014 – 4 VI 2015. More often recorded in southern Poland.

Harpella forcicella (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; 27 VII 2008 – 3 VIII 2015.

Carcinidae MEYRICK, 1906

**Carcina quercana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VIII 2007 – 26 VII 2015 (SENN 2008).

Autostichidae LE MARCHAND, 1947

***Oegoconia deauratella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1854). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2008 – 24 VII 2017 (SENN 2012).

Scythrididae REBEL, 1901

***Scythris knochella* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF34; Ht, Sg with *Cerastium arvensis*; Im 29 VII 2015 – 8 VII 2016. Recorded in nine other provinces in central and southern Poland.

***S. limbella* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2010 – 18 V 2017; det. AL (SENN 2012).

Stathmopodidae MEYRICK, 1913

***Stathmopoda pedella* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33; Aw; Im 27 VI 2017. Recorded in every other province.

Momphidae HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1857

Mompha epilobiella (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 6 V 2015 – 20 V 2016.

**M. langiella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Dm; Im 8 V 2016. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Species recorded in almost all of Poland.

M. raschkiella (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Wg, Wm; M 22 VII – 18 VIII 2015 on *Epilobium angustifolium*.

**M. subbistrigella* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 5 IV – 3 XI 2016; det. AL. Historical record from Pomerania (locality unspecified) (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in different parts of Poland.

Batrachedridae HEINEMANN & WOCKE, 1876

Batrachedra pinicolella (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Ma; Im 21 – 25 VI 2017.

Coleophoridae HÜBNER, 1825

**Metriotes lutarea* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF33, CF34; Ma; Im 4 V 2008 – 13 V 2017 (SENN 2012).

***Coleophora adpersella* BENANDER, 1939. CF34; Bu; Im 24 – 28 VII 2017; det. JB. Contemporary records from six other provinces.

C. albicostella (DUPONCHEL, 1842). CF34; Wf; Im 28 VI 2016; det. TR.

***C. alnifoliae* BARASCH, 1934. CF33; Aw; Lc 22 VII 2015 on *Alnus glutinosa*; det. TR. Recorded from almost all of Poland.

***C. alticolella* ZELLER 1845. CF33, CF34; Wf; Im 5 – 11 VI 2016; det. TR. Recorded in most other provinces.

C. caespitiella ZELLER, 1839. CF33, CF34; Wf; Im 2 VI 2016 – 18 VI 2017; det. JB, TR.

C. clypeiferella O. HOFMANN, 1871. CF34; Rd, Wg; Im 19 VII – 19 VIII 2016; det. TR.

***C. deauratella* LIENIG & ZELLER, 1846. CF34; Dm, Rd; Im 27 VI – 1 VII 2016; det. TR. Current records from eight other provinces.

C. fuscociliella ZELLER, 1849. CF34; Bu, Wg; Im 14 VI 2016 – 21 VII 2017; det. JB, TR.

C. glaucicolella WOOD, 1892. CF33, CF34; Pt, Wm; Im 2 – 18 VII 2017; det. JB.

***C. glitzella* O. HOFMANN, 1869. CF34; Pt; Lc 5 IV 2016 on *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*; det. JB. Not many records from elsewhere in Poland.

***C. granulatella* ZELLER, 1849. CF34; Tr; Im 31 VII 2016; det. TR. Contemporary records from six other provinces.

C. hemerobiella (SCOPOLI, 1863). CF34; Wf; Im 2 VI 2016; det. TR.

C. laricella (HÜBNER, 1817). CF33, CF34; Ma, Rd, Sc, Uv, Wf; Im 12 VI 2008 – 16 VI 2017; det. JB, TR.

C. limosipennella (DUPONCHEL, 1843). CF34; Tr; Lc 17 VII 2015 – 10 VII 2016 on *Ulmus* sp.; det. TR.

***C. nutantella* MÜHLIG & FREY, 1857. CF34; Ht; Im 5 VI 2015; det. TR. Records from just a few other provinces.

C. otidipennella (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Wm; Im 30 V 2017; det. JB.

***C. paripennella* ZELLER, 1839. CF34, CF43; Ma, Wm; Lc 3 IX 2015 on *Arctium* sp.; det. TR; Im 9 VII 2017; det. JB. Records from a few other provinces.

C. pratella ZELLER, 1871. CF34; Sc; Im 25 VIII 2017; det. JB.

C. saponariella HEEGER, 1848. CF33; Rd; Lc 16 IX 2017 on *Saponaria officinalis*.

**C. serratella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43; Aw, Ma, Wm; Lc 5 V 2015 on *Betula pendula*; det. TR; Im 27 VI – 9 VII 2017; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Records from all other provinces.

***C. spinella* (SCHRANK, 1802). CF34; Ma, Pg, Rd; Lc 2 VIII – 28 IX 2015 on *Crataegus* sp. and *Pyrus communis*; det. TR. Records from nearly all other provinces.

- ***C. spiraeella* REBEL, 1916. CF34, CF43; Pg; M 26 X 2014 on *Spiraea* sp. (fenestrated leaves); Lc 9 IX 2017. Records from a few other provinces.
- ***C. squalorella* ZELLER, 1849. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VIII 2012 – 30 VII 2017; det. JB, TR. Records from a few other provinces.
- ***C. squamosella* STANTON, 1856. CF33, CF34; Sc, Sg, Wg; Im 1 X 2015 – 31 VIII 2016; leg. JKK, det. TR. Recent records from only two other provinces – Podlasie and Lublin.
- C. sternipennella* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VII 2017; det. JB.
- **C. tanacetii* MÜHLIG, 1865. CF34; Wg; Lc 2 VIII 2014 on flowers of *Tanacetum vulgare*. Historical record from Gdańsk Westerplatte (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in just a few other provinces.
- C. trifolii* (CURTIS, 1832). CF34; Dm, Uv; Im 24 VI – 1 VII 2016; det. TR.
- C. trochilella* (DUPONCHEL, 1843). CF34; Rd, Wg, Wm; Im 8 V – 1 VII 2016; det. TR.
- ***C. vestianella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Uv; Im 26 VIII 2016; det. TR. Contemporary records from most other provinces.
- C. vibicigerella* ZELLER, 1839. CF44; Sc; Im 6 VII 2017; det. JB.
- ***C. violacea* (STRÖM, 1783). CF44; Pg; Lc 23 IX 2015 on *Rosa canina*; det. TR. Recorded in many other provinces.
- ***C. virgatella* ZELLER, 1849. CF34; Wf, Wm; Im 28 – 20 VI 2016; det. TR. Present-day records from just three other provinces.
- C. virgaureae* STANTON, 1857. CF34; Sc; Im 24 VIII 2016; det. TR.

Cosmopterigidae HEINEMANN & WOCKE, 1876

- ***Limnaecia phragmitella* STANTON, 1851. CF34; Bu; Im 5 VII 2012 – 7 VIII 2017. Recorded in all other provinces.
- Cosmopterix zieglerella* (HÜBNER, 1810). CF34; Sc; M 17 VIII – 9 IX 2016 on *Humulus lupulus*.

Gelechiidae STANTON, 1854

- **Aristotelia ericinella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF33; Ht, Ma; Im 18 VIII 2015 – 3 VII 2016. Historical record from Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Current records from a few other provinces in various parts of Poland.
- Chrysoethia drurella* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Ht, Rd, Wg; M 6 IX 2015 – 22 VIII 2016 on *Chenopodium* sp.; Im 3 – 5 VII 2016; det. TR.
- C. sexguttella* (THUNBERG, 1794). CF34; Bu, Ma; M 3 VII 2015 on *Chenopodium* sp.; Im 25 VII 2015 – 14 VII 2017; det. TR.
- **Isophrictis striatella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 13 VII 2010 – 29 VII 2016 (SENN 2012).
- ***Metzneria lappella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 1 VII 2015 – 11 VII 2017; det. JB, TR. Current records from almost all other provinces.
- ***Monochroa conspersella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1854). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VII 2014; det. AL. Present-day records from a few other provinces.
- M. lucidella* (STEPHENS, 1834). CF34; Sc; Im 29 VII 2016; det. TR.
- ***M. lutulentella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 4 – 28 VII 2015; det. JB. Records from most other provinces.

- Eulamprotes unicolorrella* (DUPONCHEL, 1843). CF43; Wm; Im 9 VII 2017.
- E. wilkella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sg; Im 30 VI 2015 – 14 VII 2017.
- ***Bryotropha desertella* (DOUGLAS, 1850). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 30 V 2008 – 20 VII 2016; det. TR (SENN 2012).
- ***B. galbanella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Cw with *Vaccinium myrtillus*; Im 8 VII 2016. Species recorded in a few other provinces.
- ***B. senectella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Sg, Tr, Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015 – 17 VIII 2017; det. JB. Current records from almost the whole of the country.
- ***B. similis* (STAINTON, 1854). CF34; Bu; Im 9 – 24 VII 2015; det. JB. Current records from almost the whole of Poland.
- **B. terrella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht, Rd, Sc, Uv; Im 28 VI 2015 – 9 VIII 2017; det. JB, TR. Historical records from Świbno, Gdańsk Stogi and Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from the majority of provinces.
- Recurvaria leucatella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Mw, Sc, Uv; Im 6 VII 2012 – 18 VII 2017.
- ***Stenolechia gemmella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ma; Im 14 VIII 2016. Current records from practically all of Poland.
- Teleoides luculella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Ma; Im 24 VII 2016; det. TR.
- ***T. saltuum* (ZELLER, 1878). CF34; Ma; Im 15 VI 2008; det. JB (SENN 2012).
- ***Carpatolechia alburnella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Rd; Im 23 VI 2016; det. TR. Recent records from most provinces.
- C. fugitivella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Tr; Im 10 VII 2016; det. JB.
- Pseudotelphusa paripunctella* (THUNBERG, 1794). CF34; Rd; Im 25 VII 2016; det. TR.
- ***Teleiopsis diffinis* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 27 IX 2014 – 28 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from practically the whole country.
- ***Gelechia muscosella* ZELLER, 1839. CF34; Bu; Im 8 VII – 6 VIII 2015; det. JB. Present-day records from ten other provinces.
- **G. nigra* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 9 VII 2010; det. JB (SENN 2012).
- ***G. scotinella* HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1854. CF34; Bu; Im 27 VII 2012; det. AL. Recent records from a few other provinces
- ***Mirificarma mulinella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Ht; Im 2 IX 2015; det. JB. Current records from a few other provinces in western and south-western Poland.
- Chionodes distinctella* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VII – 5 VIII 2017; det. JB.
- ***C. luctuella* (HÜBNER, 1793). CF34; Tr; Im 18 VI 2014; det. AL. Current records from a few other provinces in northern and south-western Poland.
- Aroga velocella* (DUPONCHEL, 1838). CF34; Rd, Uv; Im 29 IV 2015 – 24 VI 2016; det. JB, TR.
- **Neofriseria peliella* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sg, Wf, Wg; Im 24 VII 2016 – 14 VII 2017; det. TR. Historical records from Gdańsk and Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from ten other provinces.
- **Athrips mouffetella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 1 – 9 VII 2014; det. AL. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER, 1903). This species has been recorded in various parts of the country.

- ***Sophronia semicostella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Dm, Wm; Im 28 VI 2016 – 14 VII 2017. Recent records from many other provinces.
- ***S. sicariellus* (ZELLER, 1839). CF33, CF34; Wg, Wm; Im 18 – 19 VII 2016. Current records from many other provinces.
- ***Scrobipalpa acuminatella* (SIRCOM, 1850). CF34; Bu; Im 22 V 2015; det. JB. Current records from other parts of Poland as well.
- Cosmardia moritzella* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu; Im 1 VI 2016; det. TR.
- ***Caryocolum blandella* (DOUGLAS, 1852). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VIII 2015. Recent records from a few other provinces in different parts of the country.
- ***C. tricolorella* (HAWORTH, 1812). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VIII 2015; det. JB. Known from eight other provinces, mostly in eastern Poland.
- ***Syncopacma cinctella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF33; Dm; Im 18 VI 2017; det. JB. Current records from seven other provinces.
- ***S. larseniella* GOZMANÝ 1957. CF34; Rd, Wm; Im 5 VII 2016 – 2 VII 2017; det. JB, TR. These are the first records from northern Poland; other localities are situated farther to the south.
- ***Aproaerema anthyllidella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VII 2012 – 25 V 2014; det. XD. Present-day records from nine other provinces.
- ***Anacamptis blattarriella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 11 VIII 2009 – 1 VIII 2015 (SENN 2012).
- ***A. populella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 24 VII 2012 – 5 VIII 2016; det. AL, TR. Species known from almost all of Poland.
- ***Neofaculta ericetella* (GEYER, 1832). CF33, CF34; Ht, Uv, Wm; Im 5 VI 2015 – 28 VI 2016; det. TR. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from many other provinces.
- ***Brachmia blandella* (FABRICIUS, 1798). CF34; Bu; Im 15 VII 2014 – 28 VII 2017. Recorded in eight other provinces.
- Helcystogramma lutatella* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1854). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 9 VIII 2016 – 7 VIII 2017; det. JB, TR.
- ***H. rufescens* (HAWORTH, 1828). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 6 VII 2012 – 26 VII 2015; det. JB. Historical record from Pruszcz Gdański (SPEISER 1903). Current records from almost the whole of Poland.
- ***Acompsia cinerella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Wm; Im 25 VII 2008 – 14 VIII 2017; det. AL, JB (SENN 2012).
- ***Pexicopia malvella* (HÜBNER, 1805). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2010; det. JB (SENN 2012).

Cossidae LEACH, 1815

- **Zeuzera pyrina* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 30 VI 2007 – 4 VII 2015 (SENN 2008).

Sesiidae BOISDUVAL, 1828

- Sesia apiformis* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Rd; Im 15 VI 2007.
- Synanthedon formicaeformis* (ESPER, 1783). CF43, CF44; Ma, Wg; Im 18 VI 2016 – 3 VIII 2018; leg. JKK.

- **S. tipuliformis* (CLERCK, 1759). CF44; Ma, Pg; Im 3 – 19 VII 2017; leg. JKK. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Current records from all over Poland.
- **Pyropteron triannuliformis* (FREYER, 1843). CF34; Dm; Im 21 VII 2016; leg. JKK. Mid-nineteenth century record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in most provinces.

Limacodidae DUPONCHEL, 1845

- Apoda limacodes* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Uv; Im 3 VII 2010 – 4 VII 2015.
- Heterogenea asella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 20 VII 2017.

Zygaenidae LATREILLE, 1809

- Adscita statices* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Dm, Rd, Wm; Im 10 VI 2007 – 1 VII 2015.
- Zygaena ephialtes* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF33, CF34; Dm; Im 6 VIII 2009 – 24 VII 2012.
- Z. filipendulae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43; Dm, Wm; Im 6 VIII 2011 – 17 VII 2015.
- **Z. loti* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Dm; Im 17 VII 2014. Historical records from Gdańsk and Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from all over Poland.
- Z. trifolii* (ESPER, 1783). CF33; Dm, Wm; Im 4 VII 2014 – 2 VII 2017.
- Z. viciae* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Dm; Im 4 VII 2014 – 21 VII 2016.

Tortricidae LATREILLE, 1802

- ***Olindia schumacherana* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Ma; Im 27 VI 2008 – 15 VI 2017 (SENN 2013).
- **Spatalistis bifasciana* (HÜBNER, 1787). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 7 VI 2012 – 28 VI 2015. Present-day records from nine other provinces.
- Acleris emargana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IX 2015; det. JB.
- A. ferrugana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Pt; Im 15 III 2015 – 4 IV 2016; det. JB.
- A. forsskaleana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VIII 2015.
- **A. hastiana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Tr; 9 III 2015 – 8 V 2016; det. AL, JB, WK. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from ten other provinces.
- **A. laterana* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF33, CF34; Aw, Bu; Im 25 VII 2014 – 25 VIII 2017. Current records from most other provinces.
- A. logiana* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Mw; Im 21 IV 2009 – 26 III 2015.
- ***A. sparsana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 20 X 2013 – 25 IX 2016. Recorded in eight other provinces.
- **A. variegana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 IX 2007 – 8 VIII 2016 (SENN 2013).
- **Phalonidia manniana* (FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1839). CF34; Wf; Im 11 VII 2017. Current records from eight other provinces.
- **Agapeta hamana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm, Rd, Wm; Im 6 VIII 2007 – 18 VI 2016 (SENN 2008).
- A. zoegana* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VIII 2012.

- ***Eupoecilia angustana*** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ma, Sc, Uv, Wf, Wm; Im 15 VI 2008 – 26 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).
- Aethes hartmanniana*** (CLERCK, 1759). CF33; Ht; Im 9 VI 2017.
- A. margaritana*** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Sc, Wg; Im 19 VII 2008 – 18 VII 2017.
- **A. rubigana*** (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wm; Im 23 VII 2015 – 10 VIII 2016. Historical record from Pruszcz Gdański (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from most other provinces.
- ***A. smeathmanniana*** (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Bu, Dm, Sg; Im 18 V 2007 – 14 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).
- ***Cochylidia implicitana*** (WOCKE, 1856). CF34; Bu, Dm, Sc, Uv, Wg; Im 17 V 2008 – 28 VII 2016 (SENN 2013).
- ***C. moguntiana*** (RÖSSLER, 1864). CF34; Dm, Sc; Im 27 VI 2016 – 18 V 2017. Current records from ten other provinces.
- ***Cochylis atricapitana*** (STEPHENS, 1852). CF34; Wg; Im 8 V 2016; det. AL. Also recorded in central and southern Poland.
- **C. dubitana*** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Ht, Uv; Im 5 VI – 22 VIII 2015. Historical records from Świbno, Gdańsk and Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Known from eight other provinces.
- **C. nana*** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Pg; Im 9 VI 2009 – 10 VI 2015; det. JB (SENN 2013).
- **C. posterana*** ZELLER, 1847. CF34; Bu, Ht, Uv, Wf; Im 5 VI 2015 – 26 VIII 2016; det. JB, WK. Historical record from Świbno (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from practically the whole of Poland.
- Eana derivana*** (LA HARPE, 1858). CF34; Tr; Im 23 VI 2016; det. JB. Contemporary records from just three other provinces.
- ***E. incanana*** (STEPHENS, 1852). CF34; Sc; Im 16 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from many other provinces.
- Cnephasia asseclana*** (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33; Wm; Im 11 VI 2016; det. JB.
- ***C. genitalana*** PIERCE & METCALFE, 1922. CF34; Bu, Rd, Uv; Im 20 VII – 4 VIII 2015; det. JB. Present-day records from seven other provinces.
- **C. incertana*** (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Ma, Tr, Uv, Wg; Im 6 VI 2015 – 25 VI 2017; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from eight other provinces.
- ***C. longana*** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VIII 2015; det. JB. Recent records from three other provinces, all in western Poland.
- **C. pasiwana*** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Sc; Im 13 VII 2015; det. JB. Recorded in a few other provinces in central and northern Poland.
- C. stephensiana*** (DOUBLEDAY, 1849). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII 2015; det. JB.
- Epagoge grotiana*** (FABRICIUS, 1781). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VII 2016.
- ***Ditula angustiorana*** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34, CF44; Bu, Pg; Im ♂ 14 – 19 VII 2017. Second and third records of this species in Poland and first records of males in Poland. First record in Pomerania (SENN & KOWALCZYK 2018).
- Paramesia gnomana*** (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 20 VI 2007 – 11 VII 2017.
- Philodenides lunana*** (THUNBERG, 1784). CF34; Rd; Im 29 IV 2015.

- Capua vulgana* (FRÖLICH, 1828). CF34; Ma, Pt, Sc; Im 4 VI 2008 – 27 V 2017.
- ***Archips crataegana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu; Im 18 VII 2014 – 12 VII 2016; det. AL, JB. Recent records from almost all of Poland.
- A. oporana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 1 VII 2014.
- A. podana* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34, CF44; Bu, Sc; Im 21 VII 2008 – 6 VII 2017.
- A. rosana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Dm, Sc; Im 5 VII 2014 – 16 VII 2017.
- ***Ptycholomoides aeriferana* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1851). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2012. Recent records from eleven other provinces.
- **Ptycholoma lecheana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Tr; Im 10 VI 2009 (SENN 2013).
- Pandemis cerasana* (HÜBNER, 1786). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 15 VI 2008 – 24 VII 2015; det. JB.
- **P. corylana* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VIII 2008 – 31 VIII 2014 (SENN 2013).
- ***P. dumetana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VII 2015. Recently recorded in nine other provinces.
- **P. heparana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 28 VII 2007 (SENN 2013).
- Syndemis musculana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Ma, Pg, Sc, Tr; Im 12 VI 2008 – 5 VI 2017.
- **Aphelia paleana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Uv, Wg; Im 17 VII 2008 – 4 VIII 2015; det. JB (SENN 2013).
- Dichelia histrionana* (FRÖLICH, 1828). CF34; Ma, Uv; Im 20 VI 2012 – 8 VIII 2016.
- ***Clepsis consimilana* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Bu, Pg, Sc; Im 18 VII 2008 – 16 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).
- C. senencionana* (HÜBNER, 1819). CF34; Cw, Rd; Im 13 V – 22 V 2016.
- ***C. spectrana* (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2008 – 17 VIII 2014 (SENN 2013).
- Eulia ministrana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VI 2016.
- ***Pseudargyrotoza conwagana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 5 VII 2012 – 15 VI 2016. Present-day records from every other province in Poland.
- Bactra lancealana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF33; Pt, Wf; Im 26 V 2015 – 18 VII 2016; det. JB.
- ***Endothenia ericetana* (HUMPHREYS & WESTWOOD, 1845). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VII 2010 – 12 VII 2016 (SENN 2013).
- ***E. gentianaeana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu; Im 12 V 2012; det. JB. Records of this species from just three other provinces in western and southern Poland.
- ***E. marginana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF33; Dm; Im 24 V 2015; det. WK. Current records from eleven other provinces.
- **E. quadrimaculana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2007 – 18 VIII 2015; det. JB (SENN 2008).
- Lobesia abscisana* (DOUBLEDAY, 1849). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VII 2008 – 26 VII 2017.
- L. reliquana* (HÜBNER, 1825). CF34; Sc; Im 3 VI 2017.
- ***Pseudosciaphila branderiana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Uv; Im 20 VI 2012; det. WZ. Contemporary records from eight other provinces in Poland.
- **Hedya nubiferana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Rd; Im 16 VI 2008 – 27 VI 2015 (SENN 2013).
- **H. pruniana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Rd, Sc, Tr; Im 2 VI 2008 – 14 VI 2016 (SENN 2013).

- **H. salicella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 10 VII 2010 – 4 VII 2015 (SENN 2013).
- **Metendothenia atopunctana* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 29 IV 2009 – 12 V 2012 (SENN 2013).
- ***Pseudohermenias abietana* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Sc; Im 2 VI 2016; det. JB. Recorded in nine other provinces.
- **Piniphila bifasciana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 29 VI 2009 – 3 VIII 2015 (SENN 2013).
- Apotomis betuletana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 22 VII 2008 – 25 VII 2011.
- **A. capreana* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF33, CF44; Ma; Im 25 VI 2015 – 18 VI 2016; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- ***A. sauciana* (FRÖLICH, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 4 – 19 VII 2015. Recorded in seven other provinces.
- **Olethreutes arcuella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 12 VI 2009 – 12 VI 2015 (SENN 2013).
- **Celypha cespitana* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Sg, Wg; Im 20 VI 2016 – 5 VIII 2017. Historical records from Gdańsk and Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in most other parts of Poland.
- C. lacunana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Bu, Ma, Pt, Sc, Tr, Wf, Wm; Im 28 V 2008 – 17 VIII 2017.
- C. rivulana* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ht, Ma, Sc, Wf, Wg, Wm; Im 17 VII 2008 – 11 VII 2017.
- C. rufana* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm, Rd, Sc; Im 21 VIII 2008 – 6 VII 2017.
- ***C. siderana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 6 VII 2012 – 9 VI 2016. Contemporary records from seven other provinces.
- **C. striana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 7 VI 2008 – 16 VIII 2015 (SENN 2008).
- **Phiaris micana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Wm; Im 2 VII 2017. Historical records from Gdańsk Stogi and Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from eight other provinces.
- P. palustrana* (LIENIG & ZELLER, 1846). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VIII 2008.
- **P. umbrosana* (FREYER, 1842). CF33; Aw, Wm; Im 29 V 2016 – 27 VI 2017. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from seven other provinces.
- **Ancylis achatana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma; Im 6 VII 2010 – 27 VII 2016 (SENN 2013).
- **A. badiana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF43; Bu, Ma, Sc, Uv, Wg, Wm; Im 16 V 2008 – 25 VI 2017 (SENN 2013).
- ***A. diminutana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF33, CF34; Ma, Tr; Im 10 VI 2009 – 25 VI 2015 (SENN 2013).
- A. laetana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF33, CF34; Aw, Ma, Rd; L 4 X 2014 on *Populus tremula*; Im 18 VI 2016 – 19 VI 2017.
- **A. mitterbacheriana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF43; Bu, Ma, Uv, Wm; L 5 – 30 X 2014 on *Quercus robur* and *Fagus sylvatica*. Im 10 VI 2009 – 3 VI 2016 (SENN 2013).
- A. myrtillana* (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF34; Pt; Im 5 VI 2016.

- **A. obtusana** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34, CF44; Sc, Wm; Im 15 V 2014 – 5 VI 2017; leg. JKK; det. JB. Current records from eight other provinces.
- A. uncella** (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33; Sc; Im 19 VI 2017; det. AL.
- Enarmonia formosana** (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 26 VII 2014 – 7 VI 2016.
- **Eriopsela quadrana** (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Sc, Wg; Im 6 V 2016 – 18 V 2017. Current records from six other provinces.
- Thiodia citrana** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Ht, Wg; Im 26 VI 2007 – 4 VII 2017.
- *Rhopobota myrtiliana** (HUMPHREYS & WESTWOOD 1845). CF34; Cw; Im 5 VI 2016. Recent records from many other provinces.
- *R. naevana** (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Bu; Im 14 – 24 VII 2015; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from most other provinces.
- Spilonota ocellana** (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 9 VII 2010 – 11 VII 2016.
- **S. laricana** (HEINEMANN, 1863). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII – 16 VIII 2015. Contemporary records from all but four other provinces.
- Gibberifera simplana** (FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1836). CF34; Bu; Im 11 VII 2017.
- **Epinotia demarniana** (FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1839). CF34; Uv; Im 19 VI 2012; det. WZ. Recent records from nearly all other provinces.
- *E. fraternana** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 7 VI 2014 – 8 VI 2017. These records (2 exx.) are the first from northern Poland. Otherwise recorded only in the very south of Poland (SENN 2018).
- *E. granitana** (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1851). CF34; Cw, Ma; Im 5 V 2016 – 25 VI 2017. Recent records from eight other provinces.
- *E. immundana** (FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1839). CF34, CF44; Ma; Im 17 IX – 24 X 2015; det. JB. Recent records from most other provinces.
- *E. maculana** (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 27 IX 2014; det. JB. Historical records from Gdańsk and Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Current records from five other provinces.
- *E. nanana** (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34, CF44; Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 14 VI 2016 – 4 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from many other provinces.
- *E. pygmaeana** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Cw, Tr; Im 2 V 2016 – 30 IV 2017. Recent records from three other provinces. Also CF33 (Gdańsk Osowa); Ma; 4 V 2018.
- **E. ramella** (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF43; Ma; Im 26 VII 2008 – 7 VIII 2016 (SENN 2013).
- *E. subocellana** (DONOVAN, 1806). CF33, CF34; Aw, Tr, Wg, Wm; Im 18 VI 2008 – 18 VI 2017 (SENN 2013).
- E. tedella** (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Ma, Uv; Im 12 VI 2008 – 5 VI 2017.
- E. tenerana** (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Aw, Bu, Ma, Wm; Im 10 VIII 2016 – 20 IX 2017.
- E. tetraquetrana** (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Dm, Ma, Tr; Im 10 VI 2015 – 23 V 2016; det. JB.
- E. trigonella** (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 29 VIII 2014 – 16 IX 2015.
- *Zeiraphera griseana** (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Uv; Im 2 VIII 2017. Historical record(s) from Pomerania (no specific localities stated) (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from eight other provinces.

- **Eucosma aemulana* (SCHLÄGER, 1847). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht, Sc; Im 7 VIII 2015 – 9 VIII 2017; det. JB. Historical record(s) from Pomerania (no specific localities stated) (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from seven other provinces.
- **E. aspidiscana* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Sc, Wg; Im 8 V 2016 – 15 VI 2017. Historical records from Pruszcz Gdański and Gdańsk Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Present-day records from just two other provinces.
- ***E. campoliliana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 1 VII 2010 (SENN 2013).
- ***E. cana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34, CF43; Bu, Ht, Uv, Wg, Wm; Im 6 VII 2014 – 9 VII 2017; det. JB. Recent records from the whole country.
- E. lacteana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 2 VII 2010 – 21 VII 2015; det. JB.
- E. metzneriana* (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF34; Bu, Rd, Uv; Im 31 V 2008 – 29 V 2017.
- **Gypsonoma dealbana* (FRÖLICH, 1828). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 27 VI 2015 – 16 VIII 2017; det. JB. Historical records from Pruszcz Gdański and Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from practically the whole of Poland.
- ***G. sociana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu; Im 8 VII 2015. Recent records from six other provinces.
- Epiblema foenella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 3 VI 2008 – 24 VII 2017.
- **E. graphana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Rd; Im 7 VI 2016. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from eight other provinces.
- ***E. sticticana* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF34, CF43; Ma, Sc; Im 15 VI 2014 – 9 VII 2017. Recorded in eight other provinces.
- **Notocelia cynosbatella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 2 VI 2008 – 15 VI 2016 (SENN 2013).
- **N. roborana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2008 – 3 VIII 2015 (SENN 2013).
- ***N. rosaecolana* (DOUBLEDAY, 1850). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VI 2007 – 15 VII 2014 (SENN 2008).
- ***N. uddmanniana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 9 VI 2008 – 13 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).
- ***Pseudococcyx posticana* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1839). CF34; Tr; Im 23 V 2016.
- P. turionella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 19 V 2008 – 27 V 2017.
- **Retinia resinella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Uv; Im 22 V 2012. Historical records from Stegna and Świbno (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from seven other provinces.
- **Rhyacionia buoliana* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 4 – 6 VII 2015; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Stogi (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from all other provinces except those along the south and south-eastern borders of the country.
- ***R. pinicolana* (DOUBLEDAY, 1849). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015 – 24 VI 2016; det. JB. Recent records from all but three other provinces.
- **R. pinivorana* (LIENIG & ZELLER, 1846). CF33, CF34; Ma; Im 27 VI 2015 – 21 VI 2017; det. JB. Historical records from Gdańsk Stogi and Świbno (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from all except two other provinces.
- ***Cydia coniferana* (SAXESEN, 1840). CF34; Ma; Im 25 VI 2017. Current records from six other provinces.
- **C. fagiglandana* (ZELLER, 1841). CF34; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 2 VII 2010 – 7 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).

- ***C. medicaginis* (KUZNETSOV, 1962). CF44; Sc; Im 15 VI 2016; det. JB. Currently recorded in nine other provinces.
- ***C. nigricana* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF44; Ma, Sc; Im 27 VII – 15 VIII 2016; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- **C. pactolana* (ZELLER, 1840). CF33; Aw; Im 19 VI 2017. Also one record from CF01 (Gołubie); Pg; 14 VI 2017. Historical records from Pruszcz Gdański and Puck (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from ten other provinces.
- **C. pomonella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 29 V 2008 – 3 VI 2016 (SENN 2013).
- **C. servillana* (DUPONCHEL, 1836). CF34; Tr; Im 4 VI 2015; det. JB, WK. Historical record from the Gdańsk area (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from just three other provinces.
- **C. splendana* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 7 VIII 2008 – 13 VII 2017 (SENN 2013).
- Grapholita compositella* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF33, CF34; Dm, Ma; Im 24 V 2014 – 27 VI 2016.
- ***G. funebrana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Tr; Im 24 VI 2008; det. JB (SENN 2013).
- **G. gemmiferana* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF33; Tr; Im 13 V 2016. Historical record from Gdańsk Oliwa (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from four other provinces.
- ***G. jungiella* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Wg, Wm; Im 17 V 2008 – 11 V 2016 (SENN 2013).
- ***G. lathyra* (HÜBNER, 1822). CF34; Ht; Im 16 IV 2016. Current records from six other provinces.
- ***G. orobana* (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF44; Ma; Im VII 2014; leg. JKK. Recent records from five other provinces.
- ***G. tenebrosana* (DUPONCHEL, 1843). CF34; Uv; Im 24 VI 2017; det. AL. Present-day records from five other provinces.
- ***Lathronympha strigana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34, CF43; Bu, Dm, Ma, Sc, Uv; Im 18 VI 2008 – 28 VI 2017 (SENN 2013).
- ***Pammene aurita* RAZOWSKI, 1991. CF44; Ma; Im VIII 2014; leg. JKK, det. JB. Recent records from six other provinces.
- ***P. oxsenheimeriana* (LIENIG & ZELLER, 1842). CF34; Pg; Im 30 V 2016. Recent records from only three other provinces.
- ***P. regiana* (ZELLER, 1849). CF34; Pg, Tr; Im 5 VI 2014 – 1 VI 2015. Recorded in ten other provinces.
- ***Strophedra weirana* (DOUGLAS, 1850). CF34; Ma, Uv; Im 12 VI 2014 – 3 VII 2017; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- **Dichrorampha agilana* (TENGLSTRÖM, 1848). CF34; Rd, Wg; Im 18 VI – 5 VII 2016; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from six other provinces.
- ***D. obscuratana* (WOLFF, 1955). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ht, Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Uv, Wm; Im V 2014 – 7 VI 2016; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- D. petiverella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Ht, Ma, Rd, Tr, Wg; Im 22 VII 2015 – 25 VII 2016.
- **D. plumbagana* (TREITSCHKE, 1830). CF33, CF34; Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 23 V 2016 – 25 VI 2017; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from seven other provinces.

- ***D. plumbana* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34, CF44; Dm, Ht, Ma, Sc; Im 24 V 2015 – 9 VI 2017; det. JB. Recent records from eight other provinces.
- ***D. simpliciana* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 7 VIII 2015 – 24 VII 2017; det. JB. Recorded in nearly all other regions of Poland.
- D. vancouverana* MCDUNNOUGH, 1935. CF34; Bu, Sc, Wg; Im 16 VII 2015 – 21 VII 2016; det. JB.

Choreutidae STANTON, 1854

- ***Anthophila fabriciana* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF33, CF34; Ma, Rd; Im 13 VI 2008 – 25 VI 2015 (SENN 2012).
- **Choreutis pariana* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 30 III 2009 – 30 VI 2014 (SENN 2012).

Schreckensteiniidae FLETCHER, 1929

- **Schreckensteinia festaliella* (HÜBNER, 1819). CF34; Rd; Im 13 V 2015. Historical records from Gdańsk Stogi and Stegna (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from five other provinces.

Epermeniidae SPULER, 1910

- ***Epermenia chaerophyllella* (GOEZE, 1783). CF34; Sc; Im 9 V 2015; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- ***E. illigerella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF33; Aw; Im 27 VI 2017. Contemporary records from ten other provinces.

Douglasiidae HEINEMANN & WOCKE, 1876

- **Tinagma ocnorostomella* (STANTON, 1850). CF34; Wg; Im 14 – 18 VI 2016; det. JB. Historical record from Gdańsk Orunia. Current records from seven other provinces.

Alucitidae LINNAEUS, 1758

- **Alucita hexadactyla* LINNAEUS 1758. CF34; Bu, Pg; L 12 VII 2011 – 25 VI 2012 on *Lonicera sempervirens*; Im 1 V 2007 – 6 V 2017 (SENN 2008).

Pterophoridae ZELLER, 1841

- Platyptilia gonodactyla* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VI 2008 – 17 VIII 2014.
- Gillmeria ochrodactyla* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2007 – 27 VII 2014.
- G. pallidactyla* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF34; Bu, Dm; Im 9 VI 2007 – 8 VIII 2015.
- Amblyptilia acanthodactyla* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF44; Ma; Im 24 X 2015.
- ***Stenoptilia bipunctidactyla* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Dm; Im 3 VII 2016. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- S. pterodactyla* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Dm, Rd; Im 18 VI 2008 – 20 VI 2016.
- **Cnaemidophorus rhododactyla* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2007 – 12 VII 2015 (SENN 2008).
- ***Oxyptilus distans* (ZELLER, 1847). CF34; Bu, Dm; Im 8 – 21 VIII 2016; det. JB. Recent records from eight other provinces.
- **O. parvidactyla* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF33, CF34; Ht, Rd, Uv; Im 27 VI 2015 – 19 VI 2017. Historical record from the Gdańsk area (SPEISER 1903). Current records from eight other provinces.

- O. pilosellae* (ZELLER, 1841). CF34; Bu, Dm, Uv; Im 21 VI 2008 – 30 VI 2012.
- **O. tristis* (ZELLER, 1841). CF34; Dm; Im 23 V 2008 (SENN 2012).
- Buckleria paludum* (ZELLER, 1839). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VII 2017; det. JB.
- ***Hellinsia didactylites* (STRÖM, 1873). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sc, Wm; Im 4 VI 2008 – 27 V 2016 (SENN 2012).
- H. lienigianus* (ZELLER, 1852). CF34; Bu; Im 13 VII 2014 – 14 VII 2015.
- Emmelina monodactyla* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 IV 2008 – 28 IV 2015.
- Pterophorus pentadactyla* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 19 VI 2008 – 4 VII 2015.

Pyralidae LATREILLE, 1902

- Aphomia sociella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 9 V 2008 – 17 V 2018.
- A. zelleri* JOANNIS, 1932. CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 6 VIII 2013 – 19 VI 2018.
- Achroia grisella* (FABRICIUS, 1784). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2015; det. JB.
- Synaphe punctalis* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VIII 2007 – 19 VII 2015.
- Pyralis farinalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2007 – 6 VII 2015.
- P. regalis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 11 VIII 2007 – 4 VII 2015.
- **Aglossa pinguinalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 22 VI 2007 – 21 VI 2018 (SENN 2008).
- Hypsopygia costalis* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2008 – 13 VII 2015.
- H. glaucinalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VII 2008 – 8 VII 2015.
- Endotricha flammealis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 24 VII 2008 – 22 VII 2015.
- ‡*Cryptoblabes gnidiella* (MILLIÈRE, 1867). CF34; Bu; Im ex l. 4 X 2016. Bred from a caterpillar in a pomegranate fruit imported from Spain.
- Sciota adelphella* (FISCHER VON RÖSLERSTAMM, 1836). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 23 VI 2009 – 20 VII 2017.
- **S. hostilis* (STEPHENS, 1834). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VII 2015. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Recorded in nearly every other region in Poland.
- ***Oncocera semirubella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm, Wg; Im 8 VIII 2008 – 22 VII 2015 (SENN 2012).
- Dioryctria abietella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 25 VII 2008 – 24 VI 2017.
- D. sylvestrella* (RATZEBURG, 1840). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII – 10 VIII 2015; det. JB.
- **Phycita roborella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 26 VII 2012 – 4 VIII 2015; det. JB. Historical records from Gdańsk Orunia and Wrzeszcz (SPEISER 1903). Present throughout Poland.
- ***Nephoterix angustella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 28 VI 2015; det. JB. Recorded in all but two other provinces.
- ***Acrobasis advenella* (ZINCKEN, 1818). CF34; Rd; Im 5 V 2016. Present in all provinces.
- ***A. consociella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 15 X 2014 – 5 VIII 2015. Recent records from all but three other provinces.
- ***Myelois circumvoluta* (FOURCROY, 1785). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 20 VII 2010 – 24 VI 2016 (SENN 2012).

- Assara terebrella* (ZINCKEN, 1818). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VIII 2009.
- Nyctegretis lineana* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 30 VII 2013 – 4 VIII 2016.
- ***Homoeosoma nimbella* (DUPONCHEL, 1837). CF34; Ht; Im 3 VII 2017; det. JB. Current records from eleven other provinces.
- H. sinuella* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF44; Ma; Im VI 2014; det. AL.
- Phycitodes binaevella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 14 VIII 2017.
- ***P. maritima* (TENGGSTRÖM, 1848). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 13 VI 2008 – 29 VI 2014; det. JB (SENN 2012).
- Plodia interpunctella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 14 VI 2015 – 20 I 2018.
- ***Ephestia elutella* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VII 2015 – 3 IX 2016; det. JB. Recent records from nine other provinces.
- ***E. kuehniella* ZELLER, 1879. CF34; Bu; Im 24 III 2012. Contemporary records from seven other provinces.

Crambidae LATREILLE, 1810

- Cynaeda dentalis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VII 2008.
- Evergestis extimalis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2011 – 27 VII 2012.
- ***E. forficalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VI 2007 – 20 VIII 2015 (SENN 2008).
- ***E. limbata* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VII 2017. Recent records from eleven other provinces.
- E. pallidata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 7 VIII 2015 – 10 VIII 2016.
- ***Pyrausta aerealis* (HÜBNER, 1793). CF34; Uv; Im 3 VII 2017. Recent records from ten other provinces.
- P. aurata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Ma; Im 7 VI 2012.
- P. despicata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Dm, Ht, Uv; Im 6 VII 2012 – 16 VII 2016.
- Loxostege sticticalis* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Uv, Wg; Im 5 VIII 2008 – 31 VII 2016.
- ***Sitochroa palealis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Dm; Im 30 VI 2014 – 1 VII 2016. Recorded in all regions of Poland.
- S. verticalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Dm, Uv; Im 4 VI 2007 – 2 VI 2016.
- Psammotis pulveralis* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VII 2014; det. AL.
- Anania coronata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 28 VI 2009 – 24 VI 2016.
- A. hortulata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Pg; Im 29 V 2007 – 6 VI 2015.
- ***A. stachydalis* (GERMAR, 1821). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Mw; Im 2 VII 2011 – 24 VII 2016. Not recorded in just four provinces of Poland.
- Ostrinia nubilalis* (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 10 VII 2010 – 29 VII 2016.
- ***Udea fulvalis* (HÜBNER, 1809). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 2 VII 2007 – 19 VI 2018 (SENN 2008).
- U. lutealis* (HÜBNER, 1809). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ht, Ma, Sg, Wf, Wg; Im 4 VIII 2007 – 13 VIII 2017.
- U. olivalis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 3 VI 2008 – 19 VI 2012.
- **U. prunalis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 17 VII 2008 – 11 VII 2016 (SENN 2012).

- Pleuroptya ruralis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ma, Uv; Im 18 VII 2008 – 4 VIII 2015.
- Agrotera nemoralis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2012 – 18 VI 2015.
- Nomophila noctuella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Wg; Im 10 – 13 IX 2010.
- ***Scoparia ambigualis* (TREITSCHKE, 1829). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 3 VI 2008 – 17 VI 2013.
Recent records from practically all other provinces.
- ***S. basistrigalis* KNAGGS, 1866. CF34, CF43; Bu, Tr; Im 3 VIII 2015 – 9 VI 2016. Not recorded in just one other province.
- S. pyralella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Dm, Rd; Im 10 VI 2007 – 27 VI 2016.
- Eudonia lacustrata* (PANZER, 1804). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VI 2007 – 30 VI 2016.
- ***E. mercurella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 30 VII 2008 – 26 VIII 2017. Recent records from all but two other provinces.
- ***E. pallida* (CURTIS, 1827). CF34; Bu; Im 11 VII 2016. Current records from all except two other provinces.
- E. truncicolella* (STAINTON, 1849). CF34; Bu; Im 18 VIII 2012.
- Chilo phragmitella* (HÜBNER, 1805). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VII 2012.
- Calamotropha paludella* (HÜBNER, 1824). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2008 – 11 VII 2017.
- Chrysoteuchia culmella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF34; Bu, Dm, Pt, Uv; Im 13 VI 2007 – 4 VII 2015.
- Crambus heringiellus* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1848). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VII 2009 – 26 VII 2015.
- C. lathoniellus* (ZINCKEN, 1817). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ma, Wm; Im 13 VI 2007 – 30 V 2017.
- C. pascuella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Ma; Im 13 VI 2007 – 21 VI 2017.
- C. perlella* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Dm, Uv; Im 2 VII 2007 – 7 VII 2017.
- C. pratella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sg; Im 16 VI 2013 – 25 V 2016.
- C. uliginosellus* ZELLER, 1850. CF33; Pt; Im 21 VI 2014 – 25 VI 2015.
- Agriphila geniculea* (HAWORTH, 1811). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sg; Im 9 VIII 2012 – 1 IX 2015 (SENN 2014).
- A. inquinatella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ht, Ma; Im 8 VIII 2007 – 1 VIII 2016.
- A. poliellus* (TREITSCHKE, 1832). CF33; Sg; Im 1 IX 2015.
- A. selasella* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 6 IX 2014 – 25 VII 2016.
- A. straminella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht, Wm; Im 6 VIII 2007 – 28 VII 2016.
- A. tristella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ht; Im 28 VII 2007 – 5 VIII 2016.
- Catoptria falsella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 2 VIII 2007 – 7 VII 2017.
- C. margaritella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Pt; Im 24 VII 2009 – 8 VII 2016.
- C. pinella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sc, Uv; Im 25 VII 2012 – 13 VII 2015.
- C. permutatellus* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1848). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VII 2015; det. JB.

***Catoptria verellus* (ZINCKEN, 1817). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015. Contemporary records from all other provinces except one.

Thysanotia chrysonuchella (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Dm; Im 20 V 2009.

Pediasia contaminella (HÜBNER, 1796). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 24 VII 2009 – 25 VII 2016.

P. luteella (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 18 VI 2007 – 12 VII 2010.

Platytes alpinella (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VII 2015 – 21 VIII 2016.

P. cerussella (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Cw, Dm, Rd, Wg; Im 18 VI 2012 – 2 VII 2017.

Donacaula forficella (THUNBERG, 1794). CF34; Bu; Im 8 VII 2010.

D. mucronella (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VI 2007 – 12 VII 2010.

Elophila nymphaea (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wf; Im 13 VIII 2007 – 18 VI 2017.

Nymphula nitidulata (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 3 VIII 2007 – 24 VI 2016.

Cataclysta lemnata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Pg, Uv; Im 12 VII 2007 – 30 VI 2017.

Paraponyx stratiotata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VIII 2010 – 12 VII 2016.

Data on the five butterfly families Hesperidae, Papilionidae, Pieridae, Lycaenidae and Nymphalidae are based on SENN (2015).

Hesperidae LATREILLE, 1809

Carcharodus alceae (ESPER, 1780). CF24, CF34, CF44; Rd, Wg; Im 26 V 2009 – 3 VIII 2013.

Pyrgus malvae (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ma, Rd, Wm; Im 31 V 2011 – 6 V 2015.

Thymelicus lineola (OCHSENHEIMER, 1808). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 25 VI 2007 – 22 VIII 2009.

T. sylvestris (PODA, 1761). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 11 VII 2015.

Hesperia comma (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Rd; Im 6 VIII 2011.

Ochlodes sylvanus (ESPER, 1777). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 V 2007 – 9 VI 2015.

Papilionidae LATREILLE, 1802

Papilio machaon (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 20 VII 2006 – 10 VII 2018.

Pieridae DUPONCHEL, 1835

Leptidea juvernica WILLIAMS, 1946. CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 1 VIII 2007 – 1 V 2017.

Anthocharis cardamines (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wm; Im 2 VI 2006 – 3 V 2015.

**Aporia crataegi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg; O 19 VI 2013 – 19 VI 2014 on *Crataegus monogyna* and *Sorbus aucuparia*; L 3 VII 2013 – 13 V 2014 on *S. aucuparia*, garden fence; P 10 – 13 V 2014 on garden fence, lamp-post; Im 21 VI 2007 – 10 VI 2015 (SENN 2008).

- Pieris brassicae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 24 VII 2006 – 18 V 2015.
- P. rapae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 14 V 2015.
- P. napi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 2 VI 2006 – 16 V 2015.
- Pontia edusa* (FABRICIUS, 1777). CF33, CF34, CF44, CF45; Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 27 VII 2006 – 28 VIII 2013.
- Colias hyale* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 24 VII 2006 – 15 VIII 2013.
- Gonepteryx rhamni* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 25 III 2007 – 18 VII 2018.

Lycaenidae LEACH, 1815

- Lycaena phlaeas* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 19 VII 2006 – 11 VII 2018.
- L. dispar* (HAWORTH, 1802). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 19 VIII 2009 – 24 VIII 2017.
- L. virgaureae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 6 VII 2006 – 10 VII 2018.
- L. tityrus* (PODA, 1761). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 23 VIII 2006 – 14 VII 2018.
- L. alciphron* (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF45; Dm, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 27 VI 2015.
- L. hippothoe* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43; Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 4 VI 2007 – 11 VI 2015.
- Thecla betulae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Bu, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 31 VII 2008 – 1 X 2017.
- Favonius quercus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34; Ma; Im 10 VII 2011 – 21 VII 2013.
- Callophrys rubi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43; Fw, Ht, Ma, Sc; Im 20 V 2008 – 7 V 2015.
- Satyrrium w-album* (KNOCH, 1782). CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Sc, Tr; O 17 X 2009 – 29 XII 2011 on *Ulmus* sp.; Im 1 VIII 2010 – 11 VII 2018.
- Cupido minimus* (FUESSLY, 1775). CF33, CF34; Rd, Wg; Im 25 V 2007 – 2 VIII 2012.
- C. argiades* (PALLAS, 1771). CF34, CF44; Dm, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 26 VII 2012 – 18 V 2015.
- Celastrina argiolus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 20 VII 2006 – 7 V 2015.
- Plebejus idas* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ht, Wg; Im 28 VI 2011 – 29 VII 2015.
- Aricia agestis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 25 V 2007 – 29 V 2015.
- Cyaniris semiargus* (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43; Dm, Ma, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 24 VI 2018.
- Polyammatus amandus* (SCHNEIDER, 1792). CF24, CF33, CF34; Dm, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 8 VI 2018.

P. icarus (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 26 VII 2006 – 10 VII 2018.

P. coridon (PODA, 1761). CF33, CF34; Dm, Rd; Im 6 VIII 2009 – 14 VII 2013.

Nymphalidae SWAINSON, 1827

Argynnis paphia (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 15 VII 2006 – 24 VII 2014.

A. aglaja (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 11 VI 2007 – 10 VII 2018.

A. adippe (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF43; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 17 VII 2011 – 22 VII 2014.

A. laodice (PALLAS, 1771). CF24, CF33, CF34; Ma, Pt, Wf, Wm; Im 10 VIII 2007 – 3 VIII 2013.

Issoria lathonia (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 6 VII 2006 – 9 VIII 2014.

Brenthis ino (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF45; Pt, Rd, Wg, Wm; Im 17 VI 2009 – 2 VII 2017.

Boloria selene (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF44; Ht, Pt, Wg, Wm; Im 4 VI 2007 – 8 VI 2014.

Vanessa atalanta (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 19 VII 2006 – 11 VII 2018.

V. cardui (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 25 VI 2006 – 24 IX 2018.

Aglais io (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 17 VII 2006 – 18 VII 2018.

A. urticae (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 11 VII 2018.

Polygonia c-album (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 15 VII 2006 – 19 IX 2017.

Araschnia levana (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Mw, Pg, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 26 VII 2006 – 10 VII 2018.

Nymphalis antiopa (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Mw, Tr; Im 17 IV 2011 – 14 VII 2018.

N. polychloros (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw; Im 17 IV 2007 – 11 IV 2014.

**N. xanthomelas* (ESPER, 1781). CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44; Ma, Sc, Wm; Im 13 VII 2010 – 8 III 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).

Melitaea cinxia (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 21 V 2007 – 3 VI 2015.

M. athalia (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF24, CF33; Dm, Ma; Im 29 VI 2012.

Limenitis camilla (LINNAEUS, 1764). CF33, CF43, CF44, CF45; Ma, Mw, Sc; Im 2 VII 2010 – 22 VI 2011.

Apatura ilia (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF43, CF44; Aw, Ma, Wg; Im 7 VII 2009 – 10 VII 2013.

- A. iris* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Ma, Mw; Im 15 VII 2010 – 7 VII 2014.
- Pararge aegeria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Ma, Mw, Sc, Tr; Im 20 VII 2006 – 8 IX 2018.
- Lasiommata megera* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg; Im 21 VIII 2006 – 4 X 2014.
- Coenonympha tullia* (MÜLLER, 1764). CF33; Pt; Im 23 VI 2010 – 17 VI 2011.
- C. arcania* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 7 VI 2007 – 27 VI 2015.
- C. pamphilus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 27 VII 2006 – 12 V 2015.
- Aphantopus hyperantus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 5 VII 2006 – 11 VII 2018.
- Maniola jurtina* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 29 VI 2006 – 11 VII 2018.
- Melanargia galathea* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF24, CF33, CF34, CF43, CF44, CF45; Dm, Ma, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 15 VII 2006 – 11 VII 2018.

Lasiocampidae HARRIS, 1841

- Poecilocampa populi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 14 XI 2009 – 2 XI 2012.
- Malacosoma castrensis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2010 – 24 VI 2016.
- Lasiocampa quercus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ht; L 1 V 2016 on *Cytisus scoparius*; Im 27 VII 2012 – 29 VII 2015.
- Macrothylacia rubi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sg; L 31 VIII 2009 – 24 IV 2013 on *Rubus* sp.
- Dendrolimus pini* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VI 2009 – 6 VII 2015.
- Euthrix potatoria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Pt, Uv; L 11 V 2009 – 19 V 2010 on *Phragmites australis*; Im 12 VII 2010 – 20 VII 2017.

Endromidae BOISDUVAL, 1828

- Endromis versicolora* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 25 IV 2017.

Saturniidae BOISDUVAL, 1837

- Aglia tau* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 15 V 2011 – 11 V 2016.

Sphingidae LATREILLE, 1802

- Mimas tiliae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Rd, Uv; L 5 VIII 2009 – 26 VIII 2012 on a pavement, tree trunk; Im 22 V 2012.
- Smerinthus ocellata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 22 V 2011 – 4 VII 2015.
- Laothoe populi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; L 7 VIII 2017 on a wall; Im 31 V 2008 – 24 VIII 2015.
- Agrius convolvuli* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Pg; Im 22 VIII 2013.
- Sphinx pinastri* LINNAEUS, 1758. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 10 VII 2010 – 13 VII 2017.
- Hemaris tityus* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Sc; Im 15 VI 2014.

- Macroglossum stellatarum* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 14 IX 2006 – 27 VI 2018.
Hyles galii (ROTTEMBURG, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 28 VII 2013.
Deilephila elpenor (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma, Rd, Uv; L 13 VIII 2017 on a path by a wood; Im 19 VII 2014 – 2 VII 2015.

Drepanidae BOISDUVAL, 1828

- Falcaria lacertinaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 11 VIII 2007 – 2 VI 2015.
Watsonalla binaria (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 22 IX 2011 – 1 VIII 2014.
W. cultraria (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 30 IV 2009 – 10 V 2016.
Drepana curvatula (BORKHAUSEN, 1790). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 11 VIII 2009 – 4 VII 2015.
D. falcataria (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 28 VII 2007 – 4 VIII 2016.
Thyatira batis (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2008 – 3 VIII 2014.
Habrosyne pyritoides (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2009.
Tethea or (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 27 V 2007 – 4 VII 2015.
Tetheella fluctuosa (HÜBNER, 1803). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 17 VII 2008 – 28 VI 2015.
Ochropacha duplaris (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2010 – 7 VIII 2015.
Achlya flavicornis (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 12 III 2008 – 18 III 2015.

Geometridae LEACH, 1815

- Cyclophora albipunctata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 31 VII 2007 – 20 V 2016.
C. linearia (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 21 VI 2007 – 20 VIII 2016.
C. pendularia (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VI 2014 – 8 VIII 2016.
C. porata (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VI 2011.
C. punctaria (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 10 V 2007 – 3 VIII 2017.
Timandra comae A. SCHMIDT, 1931. CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma; Im 10 VIII 2007 – 19 VIII 2018.
Scopula floslactata (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu, Cw, Ma; Im 30 V 2008 – 5 VI 2016.
S. immorata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Sc, Wg; Im 30 V 2007 – 4 VIII 2016.
S. immutata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht, Wm; Im 29 VI 2008 – 4 VII 2017.
**S. marginepunctata* (GOEZE, 1781). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2016. Historical records from Gdańsk, Gdańsk Orunia, Sopot, the Kościerzyna district (SPEISER 1903), and also from the Słupsk area (URBAHN 1939). Recent records from all other provinces.
S. rubiginata (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 21 VII 2008 – 6 VI 2015.
S. ternata SCHRANK, 1802. CF33, CF34; Cw, Ma; Im 11 VI – 8 VII 2016.
Idaea aversata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 18 VI 2007 – 27 VI 2017. Both the nominate form and f. *remutata* are common.
I. biselata (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Ma, Rd; Im 31 VII 2007 – 13 VII 2015.
I. dimidiata (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VI 2007 – 13 VII 2018.
I. emarginata (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF45; Bu, Pt; Im 9 VIII 2007 – 8 VII 2016.
I. fuscovenosa (GOEZE, 1781). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 2 VII 2014 – 11 VII 2017.
I. inquinata (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2016.
I. ochrata (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wg; Im 26 VII 2015 – 17 VII 2016.

- I. seriata* (SCHRANK, 1802). CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VI 2007 – 12 VI 2018.
- I. serpentata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Dm; Im 19 VII 2008.
- I. straminata* (BORKHAUSEN, 1794). CF33; Ma; Im 18 VII 2017.
- I. sylvestraria* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu; Im 17 VII 2010.
- Lythria cruentaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Sc, Wm; Im 13 VII 2009 – 28 VI 2016.
- Scotopteryx chenopodiata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Dm, Ht; Im 2 VIII 2007 – 3 VII 2016.
- **S. mucronata** (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Ht; Im 27 VI 2015; det. JB. Recent records from most other provinces.
- Orthonama vittata* (BORKHAUSEN, 1794). CF34; Bu, Pt; Im 20 VIII 2012 – 14 VIII 2015.
- Xanthorhoe biriviata* (BORKHAUSEN, 1794). CF34; Aw, Bu, Tr; Im 21 V 2007 – 8 VII 2012.
- X. designata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF33, CF34; Bu, Pt, Wm; Im 2 V 2010 – 11 V 2016.
- X. ferrugata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 18 V 2007 – 23 VIII 2017.
- X. fluctuata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 18 V 2007 – 4 V 2015.
- X. montanata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 4 VI 2007 – 13 VI 2015.
- X. quadrifasiata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 28 VII 2007 – 24 VII 2017.
- X. spadicearia* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF43; Bu, Cw, Wg, Wm; Im 4 VIII 2007 – 7 VIII 2017.
- Catarhoe rubidata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VIII 2014.
- Epirrhoe alternata* (MÜLLER, 1764). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Rd, Tr, Wm; Im 21 V 2007 – 11 VII 2015.
- E. tristata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Rd, Sc; Im 1 VIII 2007 – 3 VI 2015.
- Camptogramma bilineata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm, Ma; Im 30 V 2007 – 10 VII 2018.
- *Larentia clavaria** (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 25 IX 2010 – 12 X 2018 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- *Earophila badiata** (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 20 IV 2014. Historical records from Pruszcz Gdański and Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903) and also from the Słupsk area (URBAHN 1939). Contemporary records from ten other provinces.
- Mesoleuca albicillata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 26 VI 2007 – 6 VII 2015.
- Pelurga comitata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 28 VII 2007 – 18 VIII 2016.
- Lampropteryx suffumata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 21 V 2007 – 25 IV 2015.
- Cosmorhoe ocellata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2008 – 29 VIII 2014.
- Eulithis mellinata* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Bu; Im 17 VI 2011 – 19 VII 2014.
- E. prunata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Pg; Im 17 VIII 2010 – 27 VII 2015.
- E. testata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 13 VIII 2007 – 20 VIII 2008.
- Ecliptopera silaceata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 4 VI 2007 – 12 V 2018.
- *Chloroclysta siterata** (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 4 VI 2007 – 18 V 2017 (SENN 2008).
- Dysstroma citrata* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 11 VIII 2007 – 21 VIII 2016.

- D. truncata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Pg; Im 30 VI 2007 – 8 VII 2015.
- Pennithera firmata* (HÜBNER, 1822). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2008 – 3 IX 2016.
- **Thera juniperata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu, Pg; Im 17 X 2007 – 16 X 2018 (SENN 2008).
- T. obeliscata* (HÜBNER, 1787). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 22 IX 2007 – 10 IX 2016.
- T. variata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 31 V 2011 – 17 VI 2013.
- Electrophaes corylata* (THUNBERG, 1792). CF34; Bu, Tr; Im 6 VI 2008 – 15 VI 2015.
- Colostygia pectinataria* (KNOCH, 1781). CF34; Bu, Cw; Im 22 VII 2010 – 2 VII 2017.
- Hydriomena furcata* (THUNBERG, 1784). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 23 VII 2011 – 19 VII 2014.
- H. impluviata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 5 VI 2014 – 11 VI 2016.
- Anticollix sparsata* (TREITSCHKE, 1828). CF34; Bu; Im 14 VII 2015.
- **Pareulyphe berberata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 22 V 2007 – 14 V 2018 (SENN 2008).
- **Hydria cervinalis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VI 2008 – 20 V 2012 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- H. undulata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Sc, Uv; Im 24 VI 2010 – 11 VI 2017.
- Rheumaptera hastata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Aw, Pt; Im 7 VI 2013 – 28 V 2018.
- **Euphyia biangulata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2008 – 27 VI 2014 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- E. unangulata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VIII 2011 – 21 VI 2013.
- Epirrita autumnata* (BORKHAUSEN, 1794). CF34; Bu; Im 10 X 2015; det. AM, JB.
- E. christyi* (ALLEN, 1906). CF34; Bu; Im 1 – 7 X 2015; det. JB.
- E. dilutata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 5 – 17 X 2015; det. JB.
- Operophtera brumata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 31 X 2007 – 12 XI 2018.
- O. fagata* (SCHARFENBERG, 1805). CF34; Bu; Im 14 XI 2009 – 6 XI 2015.
- Perizoma albulata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 3 VI 2016.
- P. alchemillata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VI 2008 – 28 VII 2015.
- P. flavofasciata* (THUNBERG, 1792). CF34; Bu; Im 21 VII 2010 – 31 V 2014.
- **Mesotype didymata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VII 2010 – 28 VII 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- M. paralelolineata* (RETZIUS, 1783). CF34; Bu; Im 12 IX 2009 – 13 IX 2014.
- **Eupithecia abbreviata* STEPHENS, 1831. CF34; Bu; Im 25 IV 2017; det. AM. Historical records from the Słupsk area, Ustka and Kostroga (Bytów district) (URBAHN 1939). Recent records from ten other provinces, all in central and southern Poland.
- ***E. abietaria* (GOEZE, 1781). CF34; Wm; Im 12 V 2016. Recent records from all except two other provinces.
- E. absinthiata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VIII 2010 – 12 VII 2016.
- E. assimilata* (DOUBLEDAY, 1856). CF34; Bu; Im 15 V 2008 – 11 IX 2014; det. MH.
- E. centaureata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 31 VII 2007 – 3 VII 2015.

- E. dodoneata* GUENÉE, 1858. CF34; Bu; Im 25 V 2009; det. AM.
- **E. exiguata* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VI 2009 – 22 VI 2015; det. JB (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- E. icterata* (DE VILLERS, 1789). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VIII 2007 – 4 VIII 2017.
- E. innotata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 11 V 2015 – 18 V 2017.
- E. intricata* (ZETTERSTEDT, 1839). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 12 V 2007 – 11 VI 2017.
- **E. lanceata* (HÜBNER, 1825). CF34; Bu; Im 30 IV 2008 – 22 IV 2012 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- **E. lariciata* (FREYER, 1841). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2010 – 30 VII 2014 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- E. linariata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 IX 2008 – 30 VI 2016.
- ***E. millefoliata* (RÖSSLER, 1866). CF34; Bu; Im 17 VII 2010 – 1 VIII 2014; det. AM (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- **E. plumbeolata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF33; Wm; Im 17 VII 2015; det. JB. Historical records from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903) and Ustka (URBAHN 1939). Recent records from all other provinces.
- E. pusillata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 8 IX 2013 – 25 VIII 2017.
- E. satyrata* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VI 2008 – 24 V 2014; det. AM.
- **E. simpliciata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VIII 2013 – 15 VIII 2017. Historical records from Malbork and Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Current records from all but three other provinces.
- E. subfuscata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht; Im 15 VI 2013 – 9 VI 2017.
- E. subumbrata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Dm, Tr, Uv; Im 11 VI 2007 – 6 VI 2016.
- E. succenturiata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 10 VI 2007 – 14 VII 2015.
- E. tantillaria* (BOISDUVAL, 1840). CF34; Bu, Ma, Sc; Im 8 V 2008 – 18 V 2017.
- **E. tenuiata* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 11 VII 2011 – 13 VII 2015; det. AM, JB. Historical records from Gdańsk and Gdańsk Oliwa (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from all except two other provinces.
- E. tripunctaria* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1852). CF34; Bu; Im 24 V 2008 – 15 VIII 2017.
- **E. trisignaria* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1848). CF34; Bu; Im 8 V 2015 – 15 VIII 2017. Historical records from Gdańsk Oliwa and Sopot (SPEISER 1903); also from Ustka (URBAHN 1939). Recent records from all other provinces except one.
- E. venosata* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2008 – 4 VII 2015.
- E. virgaureata* (DOUBLEDAY, 1861). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2013 – 10 V 2016; det. AM, JB, MH.
- E. vulgata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu, Pt; Im 21 V 2008 – 5 VI 2016.
- Gymnoscelis rufifasciata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2008 – 6 V 2017.
- Chloroclystis v-ata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 20 VII 2008 – 12 VII 2016.
- ***Pasiphila chloerata* (MABILLE, 1870). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VI 2011 – 15 VI 2016. SPEISER (1903) does not mention this species, while URBAHN (1939) gives records only from the present Polish province of Western Pomerania. Contemporary records from all other provinces but three.

- P. debiliata* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VI 2014.
- P. rectangulata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VI 2009 – 11 VI 2018.
- **Chesias legatella* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Sc; Im 25 IX 2008 – 15 X 2017 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Odezia atrata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Sc; Im 15 VI 2014.
- Euchoeca nebulata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Aw, Bu; Im 10 VII 2010 – 27 VI 2017.
- **Asthena albulata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Mw, Tr, Uv; Im 14 VI 2009 – 4 VII 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Hydrelia flammeolaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 3 VI 2010 – 11 VI 2016.
- H. sylvata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 30 VI 2007 – 4 VII 2015.
- Lobophora halterata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Mw, Rd, Sc; Im 1 VI 2008 – 17 V 2017.
- Trichopteryx carpinata* (BORKHAUSEN, 1794). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IV 2009 – 8 V 2016.
- Pterapherapteryx sexalata* (RETZIUS, 1783). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2012 – 6 VII 2014.
- ***Nothocasis sertata* (HÜBNER, 1817). CF34; Bu; Im 7 X 2011 – 8 X 2016. Until recently, this species was unknown in northern Poland. I photographed it for the first time in October 2011, and have found several specimens of it every year since then. The distribution range of this species is moving northwards.
- Acasis viretata* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 22 V 2012 – 7 V 2014.
- Archiaris parthenias* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Ma, Rd; Im 26 III 2007 – 21 III 2017.
- Pseudoterpna pruinata* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 9 VI 2008.
- Geometra papilionaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2007 – 24 VII 2015.
- Comibaena bajularia* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2016.
- ***Thetidia smaragdaria* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VII 2015. To date this species has been recorded only east of the River Vistula. I saw another one in Gdynia Chwarzno (CF34) on 22 VI 2017.
- Hemithea aestivaria* (HÜBNER, 1789). CF33, CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 9 VII 2010 – 27 VI 2017.
- Chlorissa viridata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Ht; Im 21 V 2016.
- Thalera fimbrialis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 16 VII 2011 – 18 VII 2017.
- Jodis lactearia* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Ma, Mw; Im 30 V 2009 – 14 VI 2015.
- J. putata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Cw, Wm; Im 22 V 2016 – 30 V 2017.
- Abraxas sylvata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Aw, Bu; L 31 X 2009 on *Ulmus* sp.; Im 18 VII 2011 – 26 VII 2017.
- Ligdia adustata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 26 IV 2008 – 28 IV 2015.
- Lomaspilis marginata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma, Tr, Uv; Im 15 VI 2008 – 3 VI 2016.
- Macaria alternata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Cw; Im 12 VI 2014 – 5 VI 2016.
- M. brunneata* (THUNBERG, 1784). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 26 VI 2011 – 4 VII 2015.
- M. liturata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VIII 2009 – 24 VI 2016.
- M. notata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Rd; Im 15 V 2008 – 23 VI 2016.
- M. wauaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VII 2010 – 4 VII 2015.

- Chiasmia clathrata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Dm, Uv, Wm; Im 25 V 2007 – 24 V 2015.
- Cepphis advenaria* (HÜBNER, 1790). CF34; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 21 VI 2007 – 14 VI 2015.
- **Petrophora chlorosata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Bu, Rd, Wm; Im 21 V 2007 – 18 VI 2017 (SENN 2008).
- Plagodis dolabraria* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 1 VI 2008 – 6 VI 2015.
- **P. pulveraria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VI 2007 – 4 VI 2011 (SENN 2008).
- Opisthograptis luteolata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Tr, Uv; Im 24 VI 2008 – 23 VI 2015.
- Epione repandaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VII 2008 – 29 VII 2015.
- Apeira syringaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2010 – 16 VII 2015.
- **Ennomos alniaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VIII 2007 – 5 IX 2017 (SENN 2008).
- E. autumnaria* (WERNEBURG, 1859). CF34; Bu; Im 6 X 2013 – 10 IX 2014.
- E. quercinaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34, CF45; Bu; Im 23 VIII 2008 – 17 VIII 2016.
- Selenia dentaria* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 24 IV 2009 – 15 V 2017.
- S. tetralunaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 10 V 2011 – 7 V 2015.
- **Odontopera bidentata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 19 V 2008 – 19 V 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Ourapteryx sambucaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VII 2010 – 4 VII 2015.
- Colotois pennaria* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 30 X 2010 – 26 IX 2016.
- Phigalia pilosaria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 III 2009 – 27 II 2017; only ♂♂ seen.
- Lycia hirtaria* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 8 V 2010 – 25 IV 2012.
- Biston betularia* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 21 VI 2007 – 7 VII 2017; occasional finds of f. *carbonaria*.
- B. strataria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34, CF44; Bu, Mw; Im 6 IV 2008 – 17 III 2015.
- **Agriopsis aurantiaria* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu; Im 18 X 2008 – 6 XI 2018; only ♂♂ seen (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- A. leucophaearia* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu. Im ♂ 25 III 2018.
- **A. marginaria* (FABRICIUS, 1776). CF34; Bu; Im 9 III 2008 – 10 III 2015; one ♀ on 8 IV 2009, otherwise only ♂♂ seen (SENN 2008).
- Erannis defoliaria* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Ma; L 23 V 2014 on *Populus tremula*; Im 31 X 2007 – 6 XI 2018; one ♀ on 7 XI 2010; otherwise only ♂♂ seen; all colour forms, including a wholly melanistic one.
- ***Peribatodes rhomboidaria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII 2008 – 11 VI 2018. Two generations per year (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- **P. secundaria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VII 2008 – 11 VII 2017 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Deileptenia ribeata* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 7 VII 2009 – 20 VII 2017.
- Alcis repandata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 2 VII 2007 – 7 VII 2017; f. *conversaria* as frequent as nominate form.
- Hypomecis punctinalis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VI 2007 – 10 VI 2015.
- H. roboraria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2007 – 25 VI 2015.

- Ectropis crepuscularia* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 1 V 2007 – 2 IV 2017.
- **Paradarisa consonaria* (HÜBNER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 29 IV 2007 – 18 V 2017 (SENN 2008).
- **Parectropis similaria* (HUFNAGEL, 1767). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 14 VI 2008 – 3 VI 2016 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Aethalura punctulata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 5 V 2008 – 26 V 2015.
- Ematurga atomaria* (HÜBNER, 1825). CF34; Bu, Dm, Rd, Sc, Wg, Wm; Im 23 IV 2007 – 16 V 2015.
- Bupalus piniaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Cw, Tr, Uv; Im 20 VI 2008 – 5 VI 2016.
- Cabera exanthemata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Sc, Wm; Im 30 VI 2010 – 15 VI 2017.
- C. pusaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Bu, Cw, Ma, Uv; L 10 VIII 2016 on *Alnus glutinosa*; Im 30 VI 2007 – 8 VII 2016.
- Lomographa bimaculata* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu, Tr, Uv; Im 9 VI 2007 – 19 V 2015.
- L. temerata* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Tr, Wm; Im 4 VI 2008 – 11 VI 2015.
- Campaea margaritaria* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Mw, Uv; Im 19 VI 2007 – 13 VII 2017.
- Hylaea fasciaria* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VII 2009 – 8 VII 2015; I have seen only the red form in Gdynia.
- **Siona lineata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Dm, Sc, Wm; Im 22 V 2007 – 3 VI 2015 (SENN 2008).
- Alsophila aceraria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 15 XI 2010.
- A. aescularia* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF43; Bu, Mw; Im 9 III 2008 – 23 III 2017.

Notodontidae STEPHENS, 1828

- Clostera curtula* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 11 V 2009 – 26 V 2015.
- C. pigra* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VII 2014 – 15 V 2016.
- Cerura erminea* (ESPER, 1783). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VII 2010.
- Furcula bifida* (BRAHM, 1787). CF34; Bu; Im 9 VII 2015.
- F. furcula* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 22 V – 6 VII 2012.
- **Gluphisia crenata* (ESPER, 1785). CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 3 VII 2010 – 21 VI 2018 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Notodonta dromedarius* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 4 VI 2007 – 18 VII 2015.
- N. ziczac* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 30 V 2008 – 12 V 2011.
- Drymonia dodonea* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VI 2011 – 13 VI 2015.
- ***D. obliterata* (ESPER, 1785). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VI 2008 – 13 VII 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- **D. ruficornis* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 14 V 2007 – 7 V 2015 (SENN 2008).
- **Leucodonta bicoloria* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VI 2007 – 4 VII 2015 (SENN 2008).

- Pheosia gnoma* (FABRICIUS, 1776). CF34; Bu; Im 24 VIII 2007 – 1 VI 2015.
- Ptilodon capucina* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 29 VII 2007 – 11 VI 2015.
- **Odontosia carmelita* (ESPER, 1799). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 8 V 2008 – 6 V 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Pterostoma palpina* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 21 V 2008 – 28 IV 2015.
- **Ptilophora plumigera* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 22 X 2008 – 27 X 2015 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Phalera bucephala* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2008 – 8 VI 2015.
- Stauropus fagi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 8 V 2008 – 28 VII 2015.

Erebidae LEACH, 1815

- Lymantria dispar* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF44; Mw; O, L, P, Im 6 VIII 2010 – 18 IX 2011; photo PJ.
- L. monacha* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 3 VIII 2008 – 5 VIII 2017.
- Calliteara pudibunda* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VI 2008 – 28 VI 2015.
- Orygia antiqua* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; L 5 VII 2010 – 9 VII 2014 on walls.
- Euproctis similis* (FUSSLY, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 12 VII 2012 – 20 VII 2014.
- Leucoma salicis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 15 VII 2012.
- Arctornis l-nigrum* (MÜLLER, 1764). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VII 2012 – 6 VII 2015.
- Thumatha senex* (HÜBNER, 1808). CF33; Wm; Im 17 VII 2015.
- Cybosia mesomella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Pt, Wg; Im 29 VI 2014 – 8 VII 2016.
- Pelosia muscerda* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VII 2018.
- Atolmis rubricollis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 26 VI 2010 – 24 VI 2016.
- Lithosia quadra* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF43; Bu, Ma; Im 28 VII 2008 – 11 VIII 2015.
- Eilema complana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 19 VII 2014 – 21 VIII 2017.
- E. depressa* (ESPER, 1787). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 19 VII 2014 – 29 VII 2017.
- E. lutarella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 5 VIII 2016 – 2 VIII 2017.
- E. sororcula* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wm; Im 20 V 2009 – 17 V 2015.
- Coscinia striata* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34; Ht, Wg; Im 5 VII 2013 – 27 VI 2015.
- Phragmatobia fuliginosa* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 25 VII 2008 – 3 VIII 2015.
- Spilosoma lubricipeda* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 28 V 2007 – 7 VI 2015.
- S. lutea* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VI 2007 – 15 VI 2015.
- S. urticae* (ESPER, 1789). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VI 2008 – 24 VI 2015.
- **Diaphora mendica* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 7 V 2008 – 23 IV 2014 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Diacrisia sannio* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Dm; Im 27 VI 2010 – 2 VII 2017.
- Arctia caja* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Wg; L 19 VI 2011 on *Echium vulgare*; Im 11 VIII 2008 – 10 VIII 2015.
- Tyria jacobaeae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Dm, Sc, Wg; L 6 VII 2006 – 11 VII 2018 on *Senecio jacobaeae*; Im 30 V 2007 – 3 VI 2015.
- Herminia grisealis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma, Uv; Im 14 VI 2009 – 3 VI 2016.

- H. tarsicrinalis* (KNOCH, 1782). CF34; Bu, Rd, Uv; Im 19 VI 2008 – 5 IX 2016.
- H. tarsipennalis* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 22 VI 2007 – 29 VI 2015.
- **Polygona tentacularia* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Dm; Im 3 VII 2013. Historical records from Gdańsk, Gdańsk Oliwa and Stara Kiszewa (SPEISER 1903). Recent records from all other provinces but one.
- Hypena crassalis* (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VI 2009 – 24 VI 2016.
- H. proboscidalis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma, Mw, Pt; Im 18 IX 2007 – 22 VII 2015.
- H. rostralis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 27 IV 2008 – 26 IX 2016.
- Rivula sericealis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu, Dm, Ma; Im 6 VIII 2007 – 28 VI 2015.
- Scoliopteryx libatrix* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 28 IV 2008 – 10 IV 2015.
- Eublemma minutata* (FABRICIUS, 1794). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht, Wg; Im 29 VII 2013 – 17 VII 2016.
- Parascotia fuliginaria* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2008 – 15 VIII 2017.
- Laspeyria flexula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VII 2008 – 12 VII 2015.
- Colobochyla salicalis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33, CF34; Bu, Ht; Im 10 VI 2014 – 9 VI 2017.
- Trisateles emortualis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 12 VI 2008 – 9 VII 2015.
- ***Catocala elocata* (ESPER, 1787). CF44; Bu; Im 6 VIII 2013 – 20 VIII 2018; photos PJ. Recent records from nearly all other provinces.
- C. fraxini* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF44; Bu; Im 6 VIII 2013; photo PJ.
- C. nupta* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Tr; Im 31 VII 2016.
- Lygephila pastinum* (TREITSCHKE, 1826). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VII 2015.
- Euclidia glyphica* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Dm, Wm; Im 21 V 2007 – 24 V 2015.
- **E. mi* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34, CF43; Dm, Ma, Wm; Im 29 V 2007 – 22 V 2015 (SENN 2008).

Nolidae HAMPSON, 1894

- Meganola albula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VII 2011 – 12 VIII 2015.
- **M. strigula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 14 – 16 VI 2014. Historical records from Łeba and Słupsk (URBAHN 1939). Current records from all other provinces.
- **Nola confusalis* (HERRICH-SCHÄFFER, 1847). CF34, CF43; Bu, Pg, Tr, Uv; Im 1 V 2007 – 23 V 2016 (SENN 2008).
- **N. cucullatella* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 17 VII 2008 – 11 VII 2017 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- Earias clorana* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Rd, Uv; Im 15 VI 2008 – 30 VI 2012.
- **Nycteola revayana* (SCOPOLI, 1772). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VII 2013 – 5 VIII 2017. Historical record from Gdańsk (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from all other provinces.
- Bena bicolorana* (FUESSLY, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 20 VI 2013.
- Pseudoips prasinana* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 2 VII 2010 – 4 VII 2015.

Noctuidae LATREILLE, 1809

- Diachrysis chrysitis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2007 – 19 VIII 2017.
- Macdunnoughia confusa* (STEPHENS, 1850). CF34; Bu, Dm; Im 1 VIII 2007 – 24 VII 2017.
- Plusia festucae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 3 VIII 2007 – 13 VIII 2015.
- Autographa gamma* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm, Sc; Im 30 V 2007 – 6 VII 2018.
- A. pulchrina* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2012 – 15 VII 2014.
- Abrostola tripartita* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 7 VII 2009 – 13 VII 2017.
- A. triplasia* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VII – 26 VII 2009.
- Deltote bankiana* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Dm; Im 18 V 2009 – 2 VI 2015.
- D. deceptoria* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Dm; Im 27 VI 2015.
- D. pygarga* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF33, CF34; Aw, Wm, Bu; Im 7 VII 2009 – 19 VI 2017.
- D. uncula* (CLERCK, 1759). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wm; Im 28 V 2012 – 21 VII 2014.
- Acontia trabealis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 21 VII 2011.
- Panthea coenobita* (ESPER, 1785). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2010 – 16 VII 2015.
- Colocasia coryli* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33, CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma; L 16 IX 2017 on *Quercus petraea*; Im 30 VI 2007 – 20 VII 2018.
- Moma alpium* (OSBECK, 1778). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 24 VII 2008 – 4 VII 2015.
- Acronicta aceris* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF43; Ma, Tr; L 13 VIII 2017 on *Acer pseudoplatanus*; Im 4 VI 2007 – 27 VII 2015.
- A. alni* (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF44; Aw; L 16 VII 2011 on *Alnus glutinosa*; photo PJ.
- A. auricoma* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 29 VI 2009.
- A. leporina* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII 2010 – 30 VI 2014.
- A. megacephala* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Ma; L 2 VII 2011 on *Populus tremula*; Im 28 V 2011 – 13 VI 2015.
- A. psi* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Ma; L 21 IX 2013 on *Ulmus* sp.; Im 15 V 2015 – 1 VIII 2016; det. RW.
- A. rumicis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; L 16 X 2013 on a wall; Im 12 V 2008 – 30 VII 2017.
- Craniophora ligustri* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 14 VII 2014.
- Panemeria tenebrata* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF33, CF34; Dm, Sc; Im 25 V 2009 – 16 V 2015.
- Tyta luctuosa* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Rd; Im 19 V 2013.
- Cucullia absinthii* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF44; Bu; Im 27 VII 2008.
- C. argentea* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF43; Ma; L 9 IX 2017 on *Artemisia vulgaris*.
- C. artemisiae* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF44; Wg; L 6 IX 2017 on *Tanacetum vulgare*.
- **C. asteris* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF33; Dm; L 1 IX 2015 on *Solidago canadensis*. Historical records from Gdańsk, Kwidzyn and Malbork (SPEISER 1903), and from Słupsk (URBAHN 1939). Recent records from all except four other provinces.
- C. fraudatrix* (EVERSMANN, 1837). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 15 VII 2013 – 4 VIII 2015.
- C. umbratica* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VI 2007 – 27 VII 2015.

- **Shargacucullia scrophulariae* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Ma; L 1 VII 2016 on *Scrophularia nodosa*. Historical records from Gdańsk and Kartuzy (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from ten other provinces.
- **S. verbasci* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF33; Rd; L 6 VI 2012 on *Verbascum nigrum*. Historical records from Gdańsk, Kartuzy and Stara Kiszewa (SPEISER 1903), and also from Miastko (URBAHN 1939). Recorded in all other provinces except one.
- Amphipyra berbera* RUNGS, 1949. CF34; Ma; Im 25 VIII 2017.
- A. pyramidea* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 14 VIII 2012 – 25 VIII 2017.
- A. tragopoginis* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 8 IX 2008 – 13 IX 2016.
- Brachionycha nubeculosa* (ESPER, 1785). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IV 2013.
- Allophyes oxyacanthae* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 22 IX 2012 – 20 IX 2017.
- Eucarta virgo* (TREITSCHKE, 1835). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2008 – 14 VII 2015.
- Heliothis viroplaca* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34, CF45; Dm, Uv; Im 1 VIII 2010 – 29 VII 2013.
- ***Helicoverpa armigera* (HÜBNER, 1790). CF44; Wg; Im 1 X 2017; leg. JKK. Current records from 11 other provinces. The first record of this migrant species from northern Poland.
- Pyrrhia umbra* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VI – 21 VII 2014.
- Callopietria juvenina* (STOLL, 1782). CF34; Bu; Im 21 VII 2011.
- ***Cryphia algae* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 12 IX 2015; det. JB. Recent records from all other provinces.
- Bryophila raptricula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VIII 2017.
- Caradrina clavipalpis* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 2 X 2012 – 9 VI 2018.
- C. morpheus* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 24 VI 2007 – 23 VII 2015.
- C. selini* (BOISDUVAL, 1840). CF34; Bu; Im 22 IX 2012.
- Hoplodrina ambigua* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 15 VIII 2012 – 1 IX 2015.
- H. blanda* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF44; Bu; Im 19 VIII 2018; photo PJ.
- H. octogenaria* (GOEZE, 1781). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2015; det. JB.
- Charanyca ferruginea* (ESPER, 1785). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VII 2008.
- C. trigrammica* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 28 V 2008 – 9 VI 2015.
- Dypterygia scabriuscula* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 1 VI 2011 – 25 VII 2016.
- Thalpophila matura* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VIII 2007 – 14 VIII 2017.
- Trachea atriplicis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 8 VIII 2008 – 28 V 2018.
- Euplexia lucipara* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VI 2008 – 29 VI 2015.
- Phlogophora meticulosa* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 15 VI 2008 – 16 VI 2015.
- Actinotia polyodon* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VIII 2008 – 7 VIII 2011.
- Elaphria venustula* (HÜBNER, 1790). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 8 VI 2014 – 24 VI 2017.
- Pseudeustrotia candidula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VIII 2012 – 19 VIII 2017.
- Ipimorpha retusa* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 16 VII 2011 – 20 VIII 2016.
- Enargia palaeece* (ESPER, 1788). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2011 – 28 VII 2015.
- Cosmia trapezina* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VII 2009 – 5 IX 2016.

- **Xanthia gilvago* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2008 (SENN & ŁUCZKOWSKI 2012).
- X. icteritia* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 22 IX 2011 – 31 VIII 2015.
- ***X. ocellaris* (BORKHAUSEN, 1792). CF34; Bu; Im 30 IX – 1 X 2014. Current records from all but four other provinces.
- X. togata* (ESPER, 1788). CF34; Bu; Im 5 X 2009 – 19 IX 2015.
- Tilicæa aurago* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 10 IX 2010 – 12 IX 2017.
- Agrochola circellaris* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 7 X 2010 – 18 X 2015.
- A. litura* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 10 IX 2012 – 21 IX 2015.
- A. lota* (CLERCK, 1759). CF34; Bu; Im 3 X 2008 – 20 IX 2017.
- A. macilenta* (HÜBNER, 1809). CF34, CF44; Bu, Ma; Im 12 X 2011 – 27 IX 2016.
- Eupsilia transversa* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 25 IV 2009 – 6 X 2015.
- Conistra rubiginosa* (SCOPOLI, 1763). CF34; Bu; Im 7 III 2009 – 11 XI 2015.
- C. vaccinii* (LINNÆUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 9 III 2008 – 1 X 2015.
- Lithophane furcifera* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 27 III 2010.
- L. socia* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 26 III 2010 – 21 IV 2014.
- Xylena exsoleta* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 23 X 2012 – 11 IV 2015.
- Griposia aprilina* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 23 X 2013.
- Antitype chi* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 22 X 2011 – 21 IX 2015.
- Mniotype satura* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2012 – 4 IX 2015.
- Apamea crenata* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VI 2008 – 30 VI 2014.
- A. lateritia* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VII 2012.
- A. lithoxylæa* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VII 2014 – 4 VIII 2015.
- A. monoglyphæ* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VII 2008 – 31 VII 2017.
- A. scolopacina* (ESPER, 1788). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 16 VII 2014 – 30 VII 2017.
- A. sordens* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VI 2009 – 23 VI 2015.
- Oligia fasciuncula* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 8 VI 2008 – 24 VI 2017.
- O. latruncula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 5 VII 2012 – 17 VI 2015.
- O. strigilis* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 22 VI 2007 – 5 VI 2016.
- O. versicolor* (BORKHAUSEN, 1792). CF34; Bu; Im 5 VII 2012.
- Mesoligia furuncula* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 2 VIII 2007 – 25 VIII 2015.
- Litoligia literosa* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VIII 2012 – 31 VII 2017.
- Mesapamea secalella* REMM, 1983. CF34; Bu; Im 11 VIII 2015; det. JB.
- M. secalis* (LINNÆUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 8 VIII 2016; det. JB.
- Luperina testacea* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 28 VII 2007 – 19 VIII 2018.
- Amphipoæa fucosa* (FREYER, 1830). CF33, CF34; Bu, Wf; Im 4 IX 2015 – 28 VII 2016; det. JB.

A. oculea (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015 – 15 VIII 2017; det. JN, RW.
Hydraecia micacea (ESPER, 1789). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 6 VIII 2007 – 17 IX 2017.
Gortyna flavago (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 4 IX 2009 – 28 VIII 2014.
Calamia tridens (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 8 V III 2008 – 8 VIII 2016.
Staurophora celsia (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 8 IX 2008 – 28 IX 2014.
Rhizedra lutosa (HÜBNER, 1803). CF34; Bu; Im 15 X 2008 – 11 X 2014.
Nonagria typhae (THUNBERG, 1784). CF34; Bu; Im 18 VIII 2012.
Globia algae (ESPER, 1789). CF34; Bu; Im 9 IX 2013.
G. sparganii (ESPER, 1790). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VIII 2010 – 13 VIII 2014.
Sedina buettneri (E. HERING, 1858). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IX 2013 – 27 IX 2014.
Photedes minima (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2014 – 12 VII 2015.
Denticucullus pygmina (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VIII 2008 – 15 VIII 2016.
Anarta trifolii (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34, CF44; Bu, Wg; Im 2 VI 2007 – 20 VIII 2018.
Lacanobia contigua (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 26 VII 2012.
L. oleracea (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VII 2009 – 30 VII 2017.
L. thalassina (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 18 VI 2011 – 24 VI 2015.
Hada plebeja (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 22 V 2007 – 23 VI 2015.
Hecatera bicolorata (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 21 V 2008 – 18 V 2016.
H. dysodea (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2014.
Hadena capsincola (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2014 – 24 VI 2016.
Sideridis reticulata (GOEZE, 1781). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VI 2010.
S. rivularis (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 V 2013 – 12 VII 2015.
Melanchnra persicariae (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VI 2007 – 3 VII 2016.
Ceramica pisi (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 18 VI 2008 – 3 VIII 2014.
Mamestra brassicae (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VII 2008 – 21 IX 2014.
Polia nebulosa (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 6 VII 2009 – 13 VII 2015.
Mythimna albipuncta (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 1 VII 2012 – 24 VIII 2015.
M. conigera (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 23 VII 2008 – 25 VII 2011.
M. ferrago (FABRICIUS, 1787). CF34; Bu; Im 7 VII 2009 – 4 VIII 2015.
M. l-album (LINNAEUS, 1767). CF34; Bu; Im 28 IX 2016.
M. pallens (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 17 VI 2015 – 17 IX 2017.
M. turca (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 21 VII 2010.
Leucania comma (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 25 VI 2007 – 24 VI 2016.
Orthosia cerasi (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu, Mw; Im 7 V 2007 – 19 IV 2015.
O. cruda (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 21 – 22 III 2014.
O. gothica (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 22 V 2007 – 4 IV 2016.
O. gracilis (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 5 V 2009 – 19 V 2013.
O. incerta (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu, Ma; Im 2 IV 2008 – 12 IV 2018.

- **O. miniosa* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 IV 2012. Historical record from Pelplin (SPEISER 1903). Contemporary records from all except two other provinces.
- O. munda* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF44; Ma; L 26 V 2012 on *Salix* sp.; photo PJ.
- O. populeti* (FABRICIUS, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 22 IV 2012 – 11 V 2015.
- Panolis flammea* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 16 V 2007 – 23 IV 2018.
- Cerapteryx graminis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 12 VIII 2007 – 5 VIII 2016.
- Tholera cespitis* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 26 VIII 2008 – 27 VIII 2015.
- T. decimalis* (PODA, 1761). CF34; Bu; Im 27 VIII 2008 – 29 VIII 2015.
- Axilia putris* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 7 VII 2009 – 4 VIII 2015.
- Ochropleura plecta* (LINNAEUS, 1761). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 10 VIII 2007 – 26 VIII 2016.
- Diarsia brunnea* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 10 VII 2010 – 7 VII 2017.
- D. rubi* (VIEWEG, 1790). CF34; Bu; Im 29 V 2008 – 17 VI 2010.
- Noctua comes* HÜBNER, 1813. CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 26 VIII 2016 – 26 VIII 2017.
- N. fimbriata* (SCHREBER, 1759). CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 3 X 2008 – 20 VII 2017.
- N. janthe* (BORKHAUSEN, 1792). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015 – 30 VIII 2017.
- N. janthina* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Uv; Im 4 VIII 2015.
- N. pronuba* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 26 VI 2008 – 15 VIII 2017.
- Rhyacia simulans* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 16 IX 2012 – 19 IX 2016.
- Eurois occulta* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34; Bu; Im 2 VII 2012.
- Xestia baja* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu, Uv; Im 13 VIII 2012 – 15 VIII 2017.
- X. c-nigrum* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 21 VIII 2007 – 15 VIII 2018.
- X. ditrapezium* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 3 VII 2010 – 7 VII 2012.
- X. sexstrigata* (HAWORTH, 1809). CF34; Bu; Im 15 VIII 2012.
- X. stigmatica* (HÜBNER, 1813). CF34; Bu; Im 4 VIII 2015.
- X. xanthographa* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 30 VIII 2014 – 19 VIII 2018.
- Cerastis rubricosa* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 28 IV 2012.
- Anaplectoides prasina* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 30 VI 2012 – 13 VII 2015.
- Euxoa obelisca* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34; Bu; Im 21 VIII 2017.
- Agrotis clavis* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 20 VI 2008 – 26 VI 2014.
- A. exclamationis* (LINNAEUS, 1758). CF34, CF44; Bu, Uv; Im 10 VI 2007 – 22 V 2018.
- A. segetum* (DENIS & SCHIFFERMÜLLER, 1775). CF34, CF44; Bu; Im 17 VIII 2008 – 14 IX 2018.
- A. vestigialis* (HUFNAGEL, 1766). CF34; Bu; Im 19 VIII 2012 – 21 VIII 2016.

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STRESZCZENIE

Motyle (Lepidoptera: Rhopalocera, Heterocera) miasta Gdyni (północna Polska)

Niniejsze badania motyli, pierwsze przeprowadzone w Gdyni, obejmuje okres od 2006 do 2018. Badania te wykazały 1172 gatunków (1108 motyli nocnych (94,5%) i 64 gatunków motyli dziennych (5,5%)). 236 (20,1%) zostały zanotowane dla województwa pomorskiego po raz pierwszy, a kolejne 155 (13,3%) nie zostały odnotowane od XIX-go lub wczesnych lat XX-go w. Jeśli chodzi o motyle nocne, 641 gatunków stanowią małe motyle (Microlepidoptera) z 47 rodzin, 467 gatunków dużych ciem (Macrolepidoptera) z 15 rodzin, oraz 64 gatunków motyli dziennych z 5 rodzin. Najliczniejsze rodziny to: miernikowce (Geometridae – 183 gatunków), sówki (Noctuidae – 167) oraz zwójki (Tortricidae – 160).

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